

Autonomous Implants

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Abstract

With the increasing ageing population, more implants are being used in the body. However, these implants often fail, and they suffer from lack of integration or providing proper function. There have been efforts to empower implants by employing bioactive materials, adding cellular components and integrating smart characteristics such as self-healing properties. The vision is though, to develop an implant that can mimic native tissues in their way of doing things, responding to challenges and remodeling. Such automated implants require the integration of advances made in various fields of science. Although early, there are good steps taken along this way, e.g. the development of stimuli-responsive, self-powering, self-actuating, self-healing, self-regenerating, self-aware implants. Attempts to combine more than one smart property into these implants are still at the beginning, e.g. the integration of such special characteristic requires a new set of skills and thinking, and it brings with it new challenges that warrant exploring and investment. Such an implant evolution is expected to be in stages where the first implant will be able to communicate with doctors and hospitals, then in the next stage with patients and later they will be independent, sense any disturbances and aberrations from normal early on and correct self before damage becomes irreversible. In this forward-looking review, we look at research done so far in this direction and efforts to assemble individual aspects of smart implants into a multifunctional implant of the future. We critically review the stages of material, *in vitro*, *in vivo* testing and clinical application if any. In addition, we discuss challenges facing the development of autonomous smart implants and suggest research directions and ideas.

Keywords. Autonomous implant, self-aware, self-actuating, self-healing, self-regeneration, self-forming, self-powering

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1. INTRODUCTION

Implants are being increasingly inserted into the body to repair, replace or help regenerate damaged or lost tissues and organs.^{1, 2} Biomaterials have evolved so far to be more biocompatible and smarter. At first, implants were stable and bioinert, and successful examples represent the introduction of hip prosthesis to the clinic by the end of 1960s.³ Then the discovery of bioactive materials such as bioactive glass (BaG) took us to a new concept where an implant can bond to tissues⁴. Later, multifunctional biomaterials were developed and functions such as drug releasing properties were added to implants to enable them to achieve faster and better healing^{5, 6} or treat complications such as infection.^{7, 8} With the advent of tissue engineering in the late 1980s,^{9, 10} it is becoming possible to construct tissues *ex vivo*¹¹ or *in situ*.¹² Most recently, the use of three-dimensional bioprinting (3DBP) enabled better control of cell and additive locations in the implants.¹³ Furthermore, the integration of advances made in other fields of science enabled the integration of sensors to implants that can help pick up changes in the implants themselves or in their surrounding before problems become irreversible and thus appropriate intervention can be instituted.^{14, 15} This makes implants smarter and have some characteristics that emulate native tissues. More technologies are becoming available to add more biomimetic in nature. The vision is to develop autonomous implants in future, which are smarter and have the characteristics of “living” tissues in the body. To realize this vision, such implants need to have different autonomy (autonomousness) properties, such as self-awareness,^{16, 17} self-regeneration,^{18, 19} self-powering,²⁰ self-actuation,²¹ etc. There have been recently studies that have been published to advance each of these components (properties) separately (independent of the other).²²

With the advances made in basic science including chemistry and biology, engineering including chemical, biomedical and information technology and integrated systems toward clinical applications, hybrid implants are being developed toward producing devices that can mimic native tissues in health and disease.^{23, 24} Such implants would be autonomous and function independently without the need for external intervention. To this end, such a new generation of implants has in essence to be multifunctional in nature. It needs to be self-aware,¹⁶ sensing self and surroundings,^{22, 25, 26} self-actuating where action is needed,²⁷ self-healing if they sustain damage²⁸ and communicating¹⁴ to alert the organism for further actions (**Figure 1**). With advanced tools we have today, communication can also be relayed with the outside environment for relying data on the implant and its environment and receiving external commands. Developing that concept and designing of auto-implants is a challenging task as technologies are fragmented and require appropriate integration by multidisciplinary knowledgeable teams who can carry this vision forward. The other challenge to develop these autonomous implants is the type of biomaterials that need to be utilized to produce such implants and make them biocompatible with human tissues. Although advanced fabrication techniques, such as 3D²⁹ and four-dimensional (4D)³⁰ printing, as well as self-powering systems,^{31, 32} nanogenerators and devices,^{33, 34} have enabled pursuing new direction or paths for designing auto-implants, yet the large number of medical problems we have today need a continuous integration of technological advances which will enable us to engineer the autonomous implants.

To our knowledge there is no study yet that combines all these properties. Therefore, we compiled this review to develop a vision for combining these properties toward building an autonomous implant of the future. The paper discusses individual technologies needed to produce such multifunctional devices, including key advances made in the design and development of self-

aware, self-sensing, self-healing, self-actuating, self-powered implants. We reviewed advances made in these self-functioning implants in various sections accounting their concept, mechanism, *in vitro*, *in vivo* studies and searched literature for any reported clinical trials. In addition, it discusses their characterization methods including animal experiments and potential clinical applications. Furthermore, current challenges and ways to address them are highlighted and directions for future research are introduced.

Figure 1. Concept of visionary autonomous implant of the future. A schematic showing the components of the autonomous implant discussed in the review, and their specific features and applications, which will enable the realization of autonomous implant.

2. PROPERTIES REQUIRED TO DEVELOP AUTONOMOUS IMPLANTS

Autonomous implants of the future are required to possess certain properties and functionalities, which include some common general and specific ones discussed in the following sections.

2.1. General requirements of a smart implant

2.2.1. Mechanical requirements

A successful implant should have mechanical properties that match their target tissue implanted into. Since healing is a dynamic process, where the mechanical properties of the newly formed and healed tissue change continuously, the implant properties should ideally match these changes. Matching mechanical properties can impact tissue reactions, e.g. brain³⁵ where it was found that neural implants with ultrathin polyimide substrate and silicon shuttle that have mechanical properties comparable to those of the brain tissue are more biocompatible. The low bending stiffness of these implants resulted in reduced inflammatory response traumas compared to other metal or silicon-based interfaces which have high elastic modulus than biological tissues,³⁶ while bone implants should have mechanical properties closer to those of the bone.³⁷⁻³⁹ For example, orthopedic implants need to be strong to withstand external forces and promote long term stability. However, the use of rigid implants may lead to stress shielding after implantation which may lead in turn to the resorption of the adjacent bone tissue and increased risk of loosening and even fracture.⁴⁰

In normal situations, tissues may also change with age and the remodeling process, and thus implants should be able to cope with these changes. So, this is the requirement that should ideally be met by future advanced implants and be an essential component of future autonomous implants that can undergo changes as required. On the other hand, implants in the body are exposed to continuous challenges, especially skeletal implants and thus, initial and sustained mechanical properties should be defined. Further, implant ductility is another important requirement for implant contouring and shaping. The implant should have high mechanical strength, fatigue strength and compression strength to prevent fractures and improve stability. The stress transfer between the bone and the implant plays a crucial role in synchronizing the implant with the bone or internal tissues, in order to protect them from severe internal damage. The implant should have good elasticity to ensure more uniform stress distribution at the implant and to minimize the relative movement at the interface between the implant and the bone. Similarly, implants exposed to harsh environment created by inflammation⁴¹ or acids^{42, 43}) or aqueous path (like saliva)^{44, 45} can greatly affect implant stability and may lead to its failure.⁴⁶

2.1.2. Chemical requirements

The implants should degrade or be stable as the clinical indication may dictate. For example, a hip prosthesis is required to stay permanently, which a bone fixation plate may not and hence degradability should be tailored accordingly. Surface chemistry is an important determinant of molecular and cell attachment, and consequent immune reactions that may lead to regeneration, e.g. by polarizing macrophages toward M2 phenotype or toward inflammatory reaction that may lead ultimately to the loss of the implant. In addition, chemistry of the surface can be manipulated by fading different functionalities that can selectively favor the attachment of certain molecules or cells. In addition, the matrix of the implants can include and controllably release certain agents that may control implant function, healing of fractures that may occur in the impact or induce cellular functions or tissue regeneration. Implants exposed to body fluids or factors that lead to their corrosion, disintegration or degradation such as wear debris,⁴⁷ colloidal organometallic complexes,^{48, 49} inorganic salts⁵⁰ oxides,⁵⁰ or metallic ions,⁵¹ Studies have shown that, long term use of metallic implants,^{52, 53} toxic products such as nickel (Ni), copper (Co) and chromium (Cr)^{54, 55} may be released to the body during corrosion process.^{56, 57} These factors should be taken into

consideration when designing the implant and selecting its materials and deciding on its target chemical properties. Released parts or metabolites should not have major toxicity or vital organ accumulation. Although biodegradable magnesium (Mg)-based implants are considered to be promising for orthopedic implants, release of hydrogen leads to problems such as inflammation and pain.⁵⁸⁻⁶⁰

2.1.3. Biological requirements

The implant should be tolerated by the body. Tissue reactions to such implants should be controllable and not interfere with implant function. Biocompatibility depends on factors such as material implant is made of, corrosion resistance, degradation, release of cytotoxic products, surface properties and mechanical characteristics.⁶¹⁻⁶³ The alteration of these attributes can affect biocompatibility, e.g. increased surface roughness leads to an increase in the surface area of the implant and thereby improves cell attachment and implant and its integration. Implants made of relatively bioinert materials such as metal alloys induce limited tissue response. Bioactive materials such as BaG induce the formation of an appetite layer that helps the bonding of the implant to the surrounding tissues, while biodegradable implants such as polymers induce inflammatory response which is a part of their elimination process. Stimuli-responsive materials can be controlled to behave in desired way, e.g. undergo degradation and change their shape or release their load according to need. Biological response can also be controlled by the implant material, e.g. to induce defined immune response such as proregenerative M2 macrophage differentiation and reduced proinflammatory M1 formation. Hence, controlled implant behavior and related biocompatibility represents an important aspect of autonomous implants, and it can be achieved by controlling various factors contributing to their biological behavior in a dynamic manner.

2.2. Specific requirements of autonomous implant

In addition to properties and attributes of the smart implant of the future, autonomous implants need to have also self-awareness, self-actuation, self-forming, self-regeneration, self- of which details are discussed in the following sections. So far only individual properties of self-awareness, self- healing, or self-forming or are there, with only few cases where implants combine two or more of these attributes such as spinal fusion cage implant with self-sensing and self-powering capabilities,¹⁶ cardiovascular stents and shock absorbers with self-sensing and self-powering capabilities.¹⁷ The possibility to compile these individual self—performing implants or autonomous components into one multifunctional autonomous implant is the gateway for the new implantable technology of the future. In the following sections we discuss advances made in these individual fields. The number and type of components required will be determined by the type of clinical application which guides the implant features required. In addition, the implant should be sterilizable and could be monitored using commonly used imaging techniques such as X-rays, computed tomography (CT) scans etc.

2.2.1. Self-healing

Self-healing of an implant is its capability to heal itself after sustaining damage, due to physical or chemical stresses resulting from internal or external causes. The concept of self-healing was first introduced in 1969 as *self-healing of cracks* occurring in polyvinyl acetate.⁶⁴ Later, the concept was associated with polymer composites in 2001.^{65, 66} Recently, the self-healing concept in the field of medicine reached its apex by developing several types of biomaterials with self-healing

properties.⁶⁷ The purpose of using self-healing implants is the extension of their lifetime,⁶⁸ and the avoidance of inadvertent damage to tissues that may result from implant failure or fracture. Although self-healing materials can be in different forms, studies comprise self-healing materials used as coatings of implants or as hydrogels (**Table 2**).

ii. Mechanism

Self-healing can be achieved by using either intrinsic or extrinsic strategies.^{69, 70} In the former, healing occurs due to properties inherent to the material(s) used for the fabrication of the implant.⁷¹ In the latter, healing is achieved via mechanisms and materials included in the implant, such as mending materials/agents of which release is triggered by damage of the implant^{72, 18, 19} (**Figure 2**). In the intrinsic approach (**Figure 2a-i**), self-healing can be achieved via chemical and physical mechanisms, or the combination of both. Examples of internal self-healing mechanisms include those based on dynamic covalent (acylhydrazone bonds,⁷³ imine bonds,⁷⁴ disulfide bonds,⁷⁵ metal-organic frames, and Diels-alder reactions⁷⁶), or non-covalent (such as hydrogen bonds,⁷⁷ hydrophobic, guest-host interactions, and electrostatic interactions⁷⁸) chemistries or through functionalized surface modification in implants that enhance self-healing features. Materials utilized to develop self-healing implants of this category use crosslinking mechanisms which provide easy fabrication and activate self-healing process at mild conditions.^{79, 80} Other approaches involve *in situ* electrostatic interaction between the positive charge of chitosan with the negative charge of chondroitin sulfate in chitosan and chondroitin sulfate scaffolds.⁸¹

In the extrinsic approach (**Figure 2a-ii**), external stimuli such as changes in light, temperature, or humidity lead to the release/activation of a healing agent (included as a filler, in capsules or vascular networks)^{82, 83} which initiates the repair/healing process. In one type of external approach, a vascular self-healing system is used. This system incorporates healing agents within capillaries (e.g. hollow tubes, channels or nanofibers) which are interconnected in a network like structure.⁸⁴ When such vascular system is broken, the healing agents are released in the system to initiate the self-healing process. However, these networks can be refilled from external sources or from the existing connecting vascular networks.⁸⁵ Another system is capsule-based (**Figure 2a-ii**), and it consists of micro- or nanocapsules that are composed of polymer matrix. It is based on polymerization process, which is triggered by mechanical damage of the capsule, after which the release of encapsulated initiator and reactants take place. The healing occurs when the healing agents are fill the cracks and polymerize.⁸⁶

In external mechanisms, material-producing microorganisms have also been investigated.^{18, 19} For example, the use of fungi in 3D printed structures to produce self-healing materials achieved by the growth of mycelia was demonstrated (**Figure 2a-iii and iv**).¹⁹ The growth of the hyphae across damaged sites allows the structure to self-heal cracks. Self-healing can also be achieved by using *Gluconacetobacter xylinus* bacteria-laden inks, which form cellulose networks (**Figure 2a-v**).⁸⁷ Self-healing biomaterials may also be made by employing stem cells as their building blocks, although such an idea is not practical for typical engineering applications.⁶⁷

ii. Studies

a. Concept and in silico studies

The design of self-healing requires careful consideration of their biocompatibility, mechanical properties, structure, and healing mechanism.⁸⁸ In an *in vitro* fatigue simulation study, investigated

the effect of cyclic loading on a resin-based composites with acrylic healing liquids containing microcapsule dental composite and revealed that this composite has enhanced fatigue resistance.⁸⁹

b. Material studies

In one approach, coating of implants with a self-healing layer to influence their behavior and extent durability was investigated⁹⁰⁻⁹⁴ (**Table 1**). For example, self-healing coating was achieved by embedding polyphenols on the surface of Mg implants.⁹⁵ When cracks appear in the coating, the polyphenols are released and chelate with the Mg ions to fill the defects (**Figure 2c (i)**). In addition, self-healing matrix of the implant material was investigated.⁹⁶ The first report detailing the development of self-healing synthetic materials for biomedical applications that was published by in 1998 discussed a new polymer biomaterial containing covalently bound iodine for making a self-healing drug reservoir.⁹⁶ Although several studies⁹⁷⁻⁹⁹ discussed the self-repair ability of materials before this, these studies were not specially prepared for medical application. Later, a study was published in 1996 and showed that cracks in a matrix material can be repaired by controlled release of repair agents.⁹⁸ Although not intended for medical application, a novel polymer composite with a self-healing capability that can recover its initial toughness by 75% was developed.⁹⁹ In medical applications, a self-healing polyacrylamide/gelatin-based hydrogel was investigated for its use as an artificial vocal fold implant.²⁸ *Ex vivo* experiments demonstrated successful restoration of the vocal fold (**Figure 2c (ii)**). For mechanical evaluation of self-healing materials, thixotropic studies at different levels of strains and then recovery of self-healing ability of *in situ* forming scaffold showed high viscosity (404.000 mPa·s at 0s and 0.25 % strain) indicating a crosslinked structure.⁸¹ Viscosity decreased drastically at 1000% strain for 10s. However, a rapid increase of >90 % recovery was noticed in the early stage, which indicated quick restoration of crosslinked structure in the scaffold.

c. In vitro studies

In vitro studies of self-healing properties of *in situ* forming scaffold made of chitosan/chondroitin sulfate showed significant increase in cell proliferation and migration of human keratinocytes and human dermal fibroblasts grown on scaffolds, indicating biocompatibility of the material and mechanical support it provided.⁸¹ In another study, enhanced healing of *in vitro* wounds (human dermal fibroblasts and keratinocyte cell line) that were treated with *in situ* forming self-healing poly-electrolyte complexation scaffold was demonstrated. The expression of proliferating cell nuclear antigen (PCNA) by these cells was significantly increased as compared to cells grown on chitosan (CH) and chondroitin sulfate (CS).¹⁰⁰ The use of self-healing chitosan-hyaluronan (HA) hydrogels to encapsulate neural stem cells (NSCs) demonstrated conducive microenvironment for neural regeneration.¹⁰¹ With increased HA content in the scaffolds, NSCs exhibited more migration and spread across the scaffold.

d. In vivo studies

In vivo experiments looked at the self-healing properties, biocompatibility^{70, 102} and efficacy¹⁰¹⁻¹⁰⁴ of implanted biomaterials. Tested biomaterials include polysiloxane,⁷⁰ polyurethane,^{102, 105, 106} polyethylene glycol,¹⁰³ chitosan/chondroitin sulfate,⁸¹ and chitosan-hyaluronan,¹⁰¹ implanted subcutaneously in mice^{70, 102} and rats¹⁰² or applied for treating certain conditions such as aortic aneurysm or brain injury.¹⁰³

For example, a polysiloxane sheets cross-linked with Diels-Alder bonds was found to have excellent self-healing properties and it was non-toxic when it was implanted subcutaneously in mice.⁷⁰ The biocompatibility of self-healing polyurethane sheets (healing is based on hybrid dynamic oxime-urethane covalent bonds and hydrogen bonds) was demonstrated after their subcutaneous implantation in mice and rats.¹⁰² Their efficacy for use in treating aortic aneurysm (mice), nerve coaptation (rats) and bone immobilization (rats) was also shown. Self-healing polyurethane implants were shown to be nontoxic,¹⁰⁵ and useful for use in minimal invasive surgery. A polyurethane film was thus applied on the surface of the heart in beagles.

Self-healing scaffolds consisting of polycaprolactone (PCL)-gelatin methacryloyl (GelMA) nanofiber containing dibenzaldehyde-terminated polyethylene glycol (GC-DFPEG) hydrogels and loaded with bone marrow-derived stem cells (BMSCs) were implanted into brain ischemic areas (after occlusion of middle cerebral artery) in rats. It was shown that BMSCs migrated from the scaffolds into the injured area, leading to significant reduction in the infarct area.¹⁰³ MSC laden scaffolds led to lower brain inflammation and more neurogeneration and angiogenesis as compared acellular scaffolds. Rats that received cell-containing self-healing scaffolds exhibited significantly reduction in infarct volume, extent of brain edema, and neurological deficits.

In vivo studies in mice demonstrated the efficiency of self-healing polyurethane elastomer sheet in treating aortic aneurysm, nerve coaptation and bone immobilization was shown.¹⁰⁴ *In vivo* studies in rats' skin excisional wounds have shown that treatment with self-healing chitosan/chondroitin sulfate scaffold was associated with faster wound closure, collagen content and alpha smooth muscle actin (α -SMA) and beta 1 (β_1)-integrin expression.⁸¹ The wound closer was ~89.5 % on day 10, histological evaluation of wounds performed on seven and 14 days displayed a significantly improved re-epithelization.

The efficacy of self-healing chitosan-hyaluronan hydrogel injected into zebrafish brain following traumatic injury (TBI, cavity created in the brain) led to better functional recovery (as indicated by swimming activity) as compared to fish which had only chitosan or saline injections into their brain cavity.¹⁰¹ The efficacy of hydrogel was further evaluated in a rat model. It was observed that chitosan-hyaluronan hydrogel injection led to maintaining brain tissue in the injury-associated cavity at 14 days, while with saline injections, brain tissue was liquefied at this time. Moreover, the rat treated with self-healing hydrogel showed >70% of behavioral function recovery in 14 days, which is significantly higher than that seen with saline injection (**Figure 2d**).

e. Clinical studies

No clinical reports published on self-healing implants have been reported so far. However, there is a clinical trial phase III (started June 2022, ending December 2022) on the use of self-healing hydrogel being used for the delivery of recombinant human epidermal growth factor for the treatment of oral mucositis associated with cancer therapy.¹⁰⁷ No publications of results have been identified.

iii. Summary

Different self-healing strategies such as non-living (internal or external mechanisms) and living (fungi, bacteria or other cell type-based) methods have been explored. Material based systems were used as matrix or coatings of the implants. Despite the positive trajectory in self-healing

materials, research has been focused mainly on hydrogels, while the development of self-healing autonomous implants is still in its way. Self-healing materials were studied *in chemico*.^{48, 57, 79, 108-116} Further *in vitro*^{102, 103} and *in vivo*^{70, 103, 104, 117} studies were used to examine the biocompatibility, toxicity, robustness and reproducibility of the implant.¹¹⁷ Potential applications include cancer treatment,^{118, 119} wound healing,^{120, 121} treating brain diseases,^{122, 123} and spinal cord injury treatment.^{124, 125} In addition, they can be used to develop stretchable self-healing skin mesh,¹²⁶ soft robotics¹²⁷, and wearable sensing devices¹²⁸. Because of concerns related to toxicity, robustness, and reproducibility, which not addressed yet,^{110, 122, 129} no clinical applications were pursued thus far. Self-healing biomaterials enable the conducting of stitch-less surgical procedures, allowing procedures to be carried out in narrow surgical fields such as in endoscopic surgery or intracranial operations. This makes them attractive tools that will impact future surgery.

Figure 2. Schematic illustrating: **a**) Mechanisms of intrinsic (i) and extrinsic (ii) self-healing. **(i)** Intrinsic approach includes materials that are based on bonding (covalent or non-covalent, imine and disulfide), and **(ii)** Extrinsic approach that includes (1) microencapsulation of healing agents (fillers) that activate the healing process. (2) microorganism based self-healing viz., fungal mycelial growth-based and (3) cellulose-producing bacteria-based. The growth pattern of mycelia

inoculated for five days bridge gaps in agar gels. Three-dimensionally (3D)-printed mycelium-based grids-initial state and ten days of incubation, showing clear growth of mycelia between printed hydrogel filaments. (4) Image of printed bronchial structure after damage, which was placed into medium to regrow cellulose fibers by *G. xylinus* bacterial in the printed structure and self-healed structure after three days of incubation).⁸⁷ **b)** Material studies: Coating implants: self-healing coating by polyphenols on the surface of Mg implants. **c)** *In vitro* studies: (i) Images of polyacrylamide/gelatin (PG) hydrogel vocal folds from stroboscopy showing the opening region of vocal cord during air flow from vent. (ii) *In vitro* studies using neural stem cells (NSCs) with live/dead staining in chitosan (CS) and chitosan/hyaluronan (CH) hydrogels after 4 and 72 h culture. Live and dead cells were indicated with green and red fluorescence, respectively. Dead cells were hardly observed in hydrogels after 4 h. **d)** *In vivo* studies showing the efficacy of CH hydrogel in alleviating the brain atrophy and neurological deficits in rat model. Typical weighted images of longitudinal brain for intracerebral hemorrhage (ICH) rats injected with saline or CH hydrogel for two and 14 days. The arrows (↑) showing brain tissue in emerging cavity, arrowheads (^) injected hydrogel, and star (*) liquefied brain tissue. In rats injected with saline, the remaining brain tissue was found in the emerging cavity after two days, while injured brain tissue remained in the emerging cavity for CH hydrogel even after 14 days. Figure **a-iv** is reproduced from,¹⁸ with permission from Nature 2023, **a-v** reproduced from,⁸⁷ with permission from with permission from Elsevier, **c (i)** reproduced from,²⁸ with permission from ACS, 2018, **c (ii)** and **d** reproduced from,¹⁰¹ with permission from ACS, 2020.

Table 1. Summary of self-healing materials used in the form of coatings and hydrogels, including material type, test/study type and method(s), application, and main outcome.

Self-healing implant/material	Other materials	Application	Test/study type and method(s),	Main outcome	Ref.
A. Self-healing coatings		Coating layer			
Mg-1Ca implant	Silk fibroin	Coating of Mg alloy-based bone implants	Scanning vibrating electrode technique (SVET), and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) to investigate self-healing properties.\	Fabrication of self-healing, pH-sensitive anti-corrosive silk fibroin, illustrating the preferable biocompatibility, self-healing properties, and osteogenic activity of the coating.\	93
Mg-1Ca implant	Composite coating (silk fibroin-based)	Self-healing coatings with corrosion resistance on Mg alloys for bone implant	<i>In vitro</i> corrosion behavior study. self-healing property study using energy-dispersive spectrometer (EDS)	This proposed composite coating provides self-healing properties, and it also has good biodegradation and biocompatibility properties. This study not only presents a significant contribution in enhancing the corrosion resistance of magnesium alloys, but also gives novel perspectives on the surface modification of biomedical magnesium alloys	130
Mg-1Ca implant	Functionalized Silk fibroin (silk) based coating consisting of halloysite (HNT)/phytic acid (PA)	Self-healing biocompatible corrosion resistance coatings for Mg-based implants	<i>In vitro</i> corrosion behavior analysis by Hank's solution. Self-healing properties investigated by EIS after Hank's solution. <i>In Vitro</i> analysis of Biocompatibility and Osteogenic properties	Investigation by histological analysis shows the excellent osseointegration of coated layer on the Mg alloy	131

				The degradation pattern and self-healing mechanisms of Silk-HN/PA coating were studied <i>in vivo</i> for bone implant of rat femora	
Mg alloy Implant	Polysiloxane modified Composite coating	Anticorrosion and antibacterial coating for bone implant		Cross-cut immersion tests were conducted to investigate self-healing properties. Antibacterial behavior was examined using the plate-counting method	The coating enhances corrosion resistance and also possesses antimicrobial performances. Results show that this coating has self-healing functionality of polysiloxane, which also indicates the potential to advance the use of anticorrosion and antibacterial coatings in the area of Mg alloy implants
MAO-coated magnesium alloy AZ31	Mg–Al layered double hydroxide coatings	Orthopedic bone implant materials		The corrosion resistance of the Mg alloy was investigated by the EIS method. In vitro cell culture testing was used to investigate the biocompatibility	<i>In vitro</i> , investigation shows the acceptable cytocompatibility of composite coating on the surface modification magnesium alloy by MAO technique. The MAO-LDH group has higher cell viability than others, showing better biocompatibility.
ZE21B Mg alloys stents	Poly (thioctic acid) coatings	ZE21B cardiovascular stents		Corrosion resistance was evaluated via the EIS method. SEM was used to examine self-healing properties after artificial scratch	Results show that the proposed coating layer, due to self-healing properties, provides good corrosion protection for ZE21B. Moreover, This coating layer exhibits superior antibacterial/oxidation properties. ZE21B cardiovascular stents modified by the hybrid coating can be employed for arterial stenosis operations
Mg alloy bone implants	duplex coating of plasma electrolytic oxidization/polydopamine	Dental root implant		Self-healing of corrosion resistance was investigated by using scanning electrochemical microscopy (SECM) and EIS methods	Results show that both SECM and EIS methods are reliable in investigating the mechanism and timing of self-healing of the protective coating layer. Also, the coating layer has excellent corrosion resistance, self-healing capability, and biocompatibility This

				coating layer can be a potential candidate for titanium dental root implants
Mg alloy orthopedic implants	Stimuli-responsive nanocomposite coating	Mg alloy implants for orthopedic application	<p>The corrosion resistance was evaluated using EIS, employing ZSimpWin software.</p> <p>Confocal laser scanning microscopy (CLSM) was used to examine self-healing properties.</p> <p>Mouse bone marrow mesenchymal stem cells were considered to investigate wound healing, angiogenesis assays, and biocompatibility in vitro.</p> <p>Eighteen New Zealand white rabbits were considered to investigate <i>in vivo</i> osseointegration.</p>	<p>Nanocomposite coating possesses multiple functions, including bacteria killing, osteogenesis, and angiogenesis.</p> <p><i>In vitro</i>, results show that better cytocompatibility, osteogenesis, and angiogenesis are observed under near-infrared.</p> <p>Results reveal that the Stimuli-responsive nanocomposite coating effectively promotes <i>in vivo</i> osseointegration</p>
AZ31 Mg alloy	Electrical-responsive biocompatible coatings	a bio-implant material field such as cardiovascular stent	<p>EIS of scratched coating was employed to investigate the self-healing properties.</p> <p>The corrosion resistance of coatings was investigated using the EIS test and hydrogen evolution of unscratched coatings</p>	<p>Proposed coatings owning outstanding corrosion resistance, self-healing, and biocompatibility can be a potential candidate in the field of bio-implants</p>

B. Self-healing hydrogels

Dibenzaldehyde-terminated ethylene glycol hydrogels (PEGDA)	N-carboxyethyl chitosan (CEC)	Drug delivery for hepatocellular carcinoma therapy	Macroscopic self-healing test and rheological recovery test.	Injectable self-healing hydrogel with pH-responsiveness, self-healing ability, and good cytocompatibility <i>In vitro</i> observation shows Dox release, which is beneficial for tumor therapy <i>In vivo</i> study shows rapid hydrogel formation after injection of CEC/PEGDA that can be used for cancer treatment	118
single component zwitterionic hydrogel	-	Biomedical applications	Tensile tests were carried out to examine the mechanical properties and effectiveness of self-healing. <i>In vitro</i> examination of the fusion and biocompatibility of zwitterionic hydrogels using commercial LIVE/DEAD assay kit	Hydrogel has excellent thixotropic property. Able to repair damage independent of time subjected to physiological conditions. Self-healing properties are observed without the need for any external stimulus <i>In vitro</i> study shows that it is important to highlight that the process of zwitterionic fusion did not result in a substantial decrease in cell viability	137
Injectable micelle/hydrogel composites	-	Skin wound healing	<i>In vitro</i> study to examine drug release capability Female Kunming mice were used to investigate the wound healing capability- an <i>in vivo</i> study Antibacterial activity was examined using Escherichia coli and Staphylococcus aureus methods	Appropriate stretchable and similar modulus with human skin, decent adhesiveness. The hydrogels show good self-healing properties and biocompatibility The hydrogel with curcumin accelerated the wound healing rate LIVE/DEAD Viability/Cytotoxicity Kit assay shows good cytocompatibility	120
Polymer network (IPN) hydrogel	Developed based on polyacrylamide and gelatin	Voice Recovery	A compression test was conducted to study hydrogels' mechanical and rheological properties	Considerable resistance to the dehydrated environment. Self-healing and safe biocompatibility properties	28

			<i>Ex vivo</i> study investigates the function of hydrogel for artificial vocal fold tissue (porcine skin)	Recovery of vocal tissues was observed after the implantation of the hydrogel	
Injectable thermo-sensitive magnetic hydrogel	Based on ethylene glycol	Drug delivery for chemotherapy in cancer treatment	<i>In vivo</i> results prove the proposed Hydrogel's antitumor efficacy (Female balb/c mice). <i>In vitro</i> study on L-929 cells	Excellent biocompatibility, exceptional self-healing, injectable, good magnetic responsive, and heat-inducing properties. <i>In vivo</i> results prove the antitumor efficacy of the proposed Hydrogel. <i>In vitro</i> , results show the biocompatibility and drug release of DOX. Both <i>in vitro</i> and <i>in vivo</i> studies exhibit enhanced synergistic antitumor activity	119
Hydrogel based on sodium hyaluronate oxide (SAO) and polyaniline-grafted gelatine.	Neural stem cells and donepezil	Spinal cord injury treatment	<i>In vivo</i> study on Female Sprague Dawley rats.	Results show self-healing, biocompatibility, electroactive The use of injectable hydrogels together with stem cells/drugs has shown advancements in the field of spinal cord injury (SCI) healing. This approach exhibits promise in addressing the limitations associated with conventional drug-based treatments and stem cell therapies	124
Hydrogel based on the dopamine/ β -cyclodextrin-modified hyaluronic acid (HA-CD-DA) and amantadine modified carboxymethyl chitosan	Loaded by dexamethasone (DEX)	Ulcerative colitis therapy	Inverted optical microscope analysis for self-healing properties evaluation. <i>In vitro</i> (immortalized human epithelial cell line Caco-2, immortalized macrophage cell line RAW264.7 and normal human colon mucosal	Results show self-healing, biocompatibility, and anti-inflammation hydrogels. The findings of this study demonstrate that the developed self-healable hydrogel effectively improved the symptoms of ulcerative colitis in mice models produced by dextran sulfate sodium (DSS) with a single dose of hydrogel. Moreover,	138

			epithelial cell line NCM-460) degradation and Biocompatibility analysis of hydrogels	developed hydrogel shows remarkable potential as a treatment strategy for UC therapy in clinical environments
			<i>In vivo</i> studies were done on mice (7-week-old) degradation, anti-inflammatory efficiency, and Biocompatibility analysis hydrogels	
				Results prove Anti-inflammatory, antioxidative capabilities, injectable, self-healing
O-carboxymethyl chitosan hydrogel	tannic acid modified gold nano-crosslinker	Treating Parkinson's disease	The SEM image examination of self-repairing properties <i>In vitro</i> analysis assay of antioxidative and anti-inflammatory <i>In vivo</i> analysis effectiveness of hydrogel on a rat model of Parkinson's disease	Results show that bioactive hydrogel facilitates motor function restoration and mitigates histological neurodegeneration in rats with Parkinson's disease. Notably, the effectiveness of the O-carboxymethyl chitosan hydrogel implant was comparable to that of the drug-loaded hydrogel. The results of this study provide evidence that the bioactive and conductive O-carboxymethyl chitosan hydrogel has potential as a biomaterial implant for neuroprotection and Parkinson's disease treatment beyond its conventional role as a carrier for cells or drugs

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2.2.2. Self-regeneration

Self-regenerating implant is defined as an implant that has the capability to regenerate after its decay in part or in whole. The purpose of self-regeneration is to enable continued function of the implant, such as sensing,¹⁴⁰⁻¹⁴³ actuation¹⁴⁴ or other functions.¹⁴⁵ Research in the area of self-regeneration of implants is relatively limited.

i. Mechanisms

Approaches include biomaterial-based⁸⁷ and living cell-based approaches to achieve self-regeneration in an implant.^{18, 19} Biomaterial based systems include mineralized hydrogels and mineral-polymer composites (**Figure 3a-i**). Cell-based systems include microorganism-assisted approaches include the use of fungi (**Figure 3a-ii**)¹⁴⁶ or bacteria (**Figure 3a-iii**)⁸⁷ to synthesize a biomaterial¹⁴⁷ or form structural elements to regenerate the construct. For example, one can use *Escherichia coli* can to produce nanofibrous structures,^{87, 147-149} or fungi to extend hyphae that in turn form 3D network structures and help regenerate constructs (**Figure 3a-ii**).¹⁸

ii. Studies

a. Concept

Polyacrylamide hydrogels can regenerate swollen surfaces after abrasive wear to maintain the low friction surface ability.¹⁵⁰ This ability of polyacrylamide hydrogels can be exploited for developing biomedical devices that need to keep their surface at low friction.

b. Material level

Material-based:

In one example, self-regeneration in an iontronics hydrogel was achieved via MXene and calcium chloride (CaCl₂) which endow the hydrogel with both ion and electron conductive channels.¹⁵¹ The self-regenerative ability was attained by the incorporation of CaCl₂ which has the ability to retain water for longer duration. The hydrogel retained water up to 70 days of continuous use, which is essential for the long-term stability of the hydrogel-based bionic skin sensor. Further, the hydrogel exhibited frost resistance at ultra-low temperature (-50 °C) exhibiting sensing ability at lower temperature.

Cell-based:

To produce 3D structures, a cellulose-producing bacteria, *Gluconacetobacter xylinus* was used in bioinks to 3D bioprint a bronchial tree-like structure (**Figure 3**).⁸⁷ Nutrients for the bacterial growth are already present in the ink, which enables the formation of cellulose fibers. Oxygen (O₂) required by microorganisms for metabolism is obtained from air.¹⁵² In another study, *Gluconacetobacter xylinus* was embedded in aqueous ink (xanthum gum in culture medium) for producing a cellulose fiber network in a silicone-based granular gel.¹⁵³ The bacteria remained alive in printed constructs which were capable of self-regeneration of their cellulose fiber networks after network decay. Furthermore, complex tubular structures were printed, incubated for bacterial growth and cellulose formation, and cut using a blade. When the cut ends were placed in close contact and incubated in culture medium for three days, regeneration was observed. The nutrients in the medium enabled the growth of cellulose fibers regenerating fiber network of the damaged hydrogel. The growth of cellulose fibers occurred throughout the structure, which also resulted in a smooth surface and thickening of the original geometry of fibers. The challenge is what stops

these bacteria form producing more, or they will be stopped by filling voids in the adjacent structures and close vicinity only.

In one example, bacterial cellulose composites were developed by functionalizing cellulose with cerium oxide (CeO₂) nanoparticles to achieve self-regeneration properties.¹⁵⁴ Further, zirconium was incorporated into the CeO₂ lattice to increase the O₂ storage capability of these composites. This was demonstrated using diffuse-reflectance ultraviolet–visible (UV/Vis) tracking of composites absorbance over two weeks while being immersed in water (H₂O₂). The absorption edge was dependent on the oxidation state of cerium. When the composites were immersed in H₂O₂, there was a shift in the absorption when it converted Ce³⁺ to Ce⁴⁺, the wavelength shift upon oxidation and subsequent recovery of the original absorption edge wavelength which indicated the regeneration nature of the composite materials. A complete regeneration was noticed in two weeks despite a larger concentration than those within the body (**Figure 3b**). In a recent study,¹⁴⁷ self-regeneration hydrogels were fabricated using *E. coli* as the cellular chassis and mucoadhesive protein nanofibers as an extracellular matrix (ECM). The bacterial hydrogel was harvested from broth cultures using filtration. The hydrogel regenerated itself *in situ* and grows four–fold in mass over a period of 24 hours when optimal conditions are maintained. The hydrogel was programmed to interact with specific different tissues in the gastrointestinal tract (GI) due to its genetically programmable rheological properties which enable them to retain in GI for several days because of continually regeneration like the mucins themselves.

In 3D bioprinted constructs that contained *Ganoderma Lucidum* embedded in hydrogels (agar, κ-carrageenan and cellulose-based thickener), mycelia grew between hydrogel filaments after 20 days of incubation.¹⁸ It was found that the growth of mycelia between the filaments was strongly influenced by malt concentration present in the substrate (**Figure 3a**). Mycelia grew by 0.6–0.7 mm day⁻¹ and reached a maximum healing distance of 2.5 to 3 mm, when malt was available at a concentration equal or higher than 6%. It is interesting to note that the mycelial network formation and metabolic activity can be regained even after a prolonged dormant state of as long as eight months.¹⁹

c. In vitro cell studies

Cell viability assays using human colonic carcinoma cell lines (Caco-2 cells) co-incubated with self-regenerating curli fiber hydrogel gels that were obtained from bacterial culture, confirmed their lack of cytotoxicity (**Figure. 3c**).¹⁴⁷

d. In vivo studies

To investigate the mucoadhesive properties of self-regenerating living gels, PQN4 bacterial cells entrapped in curli-specific genes (CsgA) protein-trefoil factor family 2 (CsgA-TFF2) curli fiber network were administered orally to healthy mice that were monitored by harvesting tissues at different endpoints (**Figure 3d**).¹⁴⁷ The study demonstrated that curli fiber hydrogel was expelled out after 24 hours, while the embedded bacteria was retained within the GI tract, allowing continuous regeneration of fibers.

e. Clinical studies

No clinical studies have been reported to the best of our knowledge.

iii. Summary.

Several approaches can be used to achieve self-regeneration properties in hydrogels,^{150, 155, 156} and coatings,¹⁵⁷⁻¹⁶⁰ using biomaterial-producing bacteria and fungi.¹⁴⁶ So far, there have been no studies using cells apart from bacteria to examine cytocompatibility or efficacy or animal studies. These studies are essential to demonstrate the safety and value of self-regenerating biomaterials and take them forward toward integration into smart materials and enable the development of autonomous implants in future.

Preprint

Figure 3. Self-regeneration of implants that can be achieved through: **a)** Mechanisms: **i)** biomaterial-based approach which includes, cellulose based living structures **ii)** fungi-based approach: self-regeneration by mycelial cell growth, which forms hyphal network and grid-shaped structures, **iii)** bacteria-based approach¹⁴⁷ by keeping the bacteria alive in the printed object. Engineered living materials developed into complex geometries capable of self-regeneration of their cellulose fiber network following damage. The aerobic bacterial *Gluconacetobacter xylinus* were embedded into aqueous ink to produce cellulose fiber networks

after printing into desired geometry., **iv**) tissue engineering based on O₂ generating biomaterials, where cells and O₂ source containing bioinks are combined to fabricate 3D printed constructs for regenerative therapy. **b**) Material studies: bacterial cellulose hydrogels containing Ce_{1-x}Zr_xO₂ NPs possessing self-regenerating antioxidants properties whose efficiency depends on the equilibrium population of Ce³⁺ and Ce⁴⁺ **c**) *In vitro* studies: **i**) of live hydrogel harvested into bacterial growth medium. The dry mass of live gels was measured after 24 and 48 hours, in presence of various concentration of SDS. **d**) *In vivo* studies: **i**) Illustration of self-regeneration process of live gels in GI tract of mice.¹⁴⁷ Tracking of live gel that was administered orally in mice after 24, 48 and 72 hours. Cy5 fluorescence measured in GI tracts harvested 72 hours after live gel administration. A fluorescent dye conjugated to Ni-NTA and observed its concentration in harvested GI tracts after 72 hours. The live gel composed of TFF2 protein, 6x-His tags at C-terminus, the live gel retained the dye and seen in the cecum and proximal and medial colon of mice, while original curli fibers of live gel were excreted completely by the dye. Figure **a** **(i)**. reproduced from ref¹⁸ with permission from Nature, 2023. **(ii)** reproduced from ref¹⁴⁷ with permission from Wiley-VCH, 2019; **b** and **c** reproduced from ref.¹⁴⁷, with permission from Wiley-VCH, 2019.

2.2.3. Self-reconfiguration and transformation

A self-transforming implant is defined as the implant capability to change its physical properties as needed in a self-acting internal force driven mode, without the need for an external intervention or stimuli. These transformations include morphological/mechanical change from an initial two-dimensional (2D) to a predesigned 3D shape,¹⁶¹⁻¹⁷⁰ from a relatively low viscosity to a semi-solid material, from a low rigidity and compliance to a high rigidity state,¹⁷¹ or from small parts to pre-determined assembly (**Figure 4**). Recently, considerable interest has been put into such self-forming/self-reconfigurable 3D implants, which is inspired by naturally occurring blood and lymph vessels, biodegradable *in situ* forming implants (ISFI) formed from injectable fluids have an advantage, as the procedure is less invasive. They can successfully be used for *in situ* tissue engineering cell culturing and transportation, and drug delivery.¹⁷²⁻¹⁷⁴ The purpose of having a self-transforming implant is mimic the dynamicity of tissues and enable the implant to change form or properties adapting to changes in its environment or arising requirements. This includes changes in shape in their rigidity changing from rigid to soft, to accommodate micromotion or from soft to rigid, to achieve variable-stiffness actuation. The use of self-forming/configuring materials also enables achieving minimally invasive implantation and *in situ* implant formation. These smart implants can successfully adapt to complex tissue surfaces and structures.

i. Mechanism

Self-reconfiguration, including shape change and stiffness varying, could be modulated to occur as a result of strain engineering,^{161, 163} shape memory polymer based strategy,^{162, 164-166} temperature-triggered soft-rigid phase transition of phase change metal gallium,¹⁷⁵ gelatin swelling,^{168, 170} and stiffness varying via quick mineralization.¹⁷¹ Self-assembling can be realized by magnetic force among magnets to form a predetermined macro configuration¹⁷⁶ (**Table 2**).

Self-reconfigurable membranes provide a feasible strategy to fabricate such tubular structures of different diameters.^{161-163, 168} Different cell types are used as different layers of tube walls by first patterning different cells on a 2D surface, which could undergo changes in shape and then deforming the 2D surface into a 3D structure.¹⁶¹⁻¹⁶³ For example, the technique of stress-induced

rolling membrane (SIRM) was adopted to produce tubular structures that have walls made of layers of different cell types mimicking blood vessels.¹⁷⁷ Tubular structures such as trachea, blood vessels and lymph vessels have specific 3D shape and multiple cells at specific locations. Developed tubular structures had different layers containing cells aligned either longitudinally or circumferentially around the tube, similar to the natural arrangement found in native tissues. Tubes with controllable size was produced and the cell orientation was regulated inside the tubes by topographical contact guidance. By rolling simple patterns, 2D membranes were transformed into complex 3D tubes. This method is also suitable for the fabrication of self-adjustable scaffolds that require the maintenance of defined shape for longer durations (**Figure 4ai**).¹⁷⁸ The use of shape memory scaffold is another example that allows to develop engineered cardiac patches, which can be injected into the body using minimally invasive approach. Injected scaffold collapsed during injection and regained its original shape following delivery to target location (**Figure 4 aii**).¹⁷⁹ Biocompatible twining electrode with the capability of self-climbing based on body temperature to form 3D neural interfaces is another example (**Figure 4 iii**). These electrodes can reduce the risk of nerve injury that may be caused by mechanical mismatch,¹⁸⁰ because of their self-reconfiguration property. When peripheral nerves undergo deformation, such as bending, swelling, or stretching, the twining electrodes will deform and thus the risk of nerve damage by electrodes can be avoided.

ii. Studies

a. Concept studies

An implant that can change its rigidity properties as tissues heal; to transfer load to the healing tissue such as bone would be of great importance. It is known that rigid bone implants result in stress shielding depriving bone from physiological loading it consequent weakening of the bone, implant loosening and risk of fractures. Therefore, with self-transforming implant that can undergo changes in its strength properties with time and changes in the properties of the healing bone will be a great achievement in future. Changes in the shape of the implant will also be needed so the implant can give room to the expanding healing tissue or the implant may expand to fill in the gaps left by the remodeling of the healing tissue or in other situation, where dynamics of the pathology being treated change by time such as in the treatment of bone defects, where a marginal death of tissues can be absorbed and replaced by a dynamic implant that is installed in the time when this void is not there.

Stiffness varying between either soft-to-hard or hard-to-soft is an important property of devices. Low rigidity and good compliance are required by the implants on/in soft tissues to reduce mechanical resistance, promote morphological adaptation, or accommodate organ micromotions during normal movement, while the surgical insertion process may require high rigidity property for ease of handling. For example, temperature-triggered soft-rigid phase transition devices were fabricated with gallium and used as deep brain neural probes. The device remains rigid at the temperature of the operating room, and it softens following deep brain injection. This helps the implant to accommodate micromotions occurring inside the skull during ordinary movement. The benefits of this approach are both reduced lesion size and inflammatory glial responses compared to tungsten needles of the same dimensions, suggesting that the transformative approach is more amenable to deep embedding in soft tissue.¹⁷⁵ On the contrary, high rigidity is required by hard tissue implants for structural load bearing, while low rigidity and material compliance might be ideal to morph and integrate to surrounding tissue. For example, biochemically induced variable-stiffness actuators that can take different pre-programmed forms and change from soft to rigid by

growing bone can be made. These can be utilized as morphing biological adhesives useful for the treatment of fractures, or application inside cavities to expand and initiate bone regrowth.¹⁷¹

An innovative climbing-inspired concept was introduced in the form of prototype that forms 3D twining electrodes, which can self-climb onto the peripheral nerves using smart shape memory polymers (SMPs) that can respond to body temperature.¹⁸⁰ Designing 3D twining electrodes is performed by integrating stretchable mesh serpentine wires onto a flexible shape memory substrate.

b. Material studies

In one study, tubular structure with multiple cells that can mimic blood vessels was fabricated using SIRM technique using two elastic polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) membranes.¹⁶³ The top membrane was made of cured PDMS, which is stretched to produce stress while the bottom membrane is semi-cured PDMS membrane fabricated by spin-coating of uncured PDMS. The bottom layer acts as an adhesive layer which binds with the top layer during the curing process. Developed SIRM were covered with PDMS mold embedded with microfluidic channels that can deliver different types of cells to the surface of SIRM. The cell sheet rolls up with the SIRM to produce layered wall of tube like the vessel structures. By simple rolling process 2D membranes were transformed into 3D tubes that can mimic blood vessels. The shape of the tube is supported by the balance of internal stress and strain. Moreover, it reforms itself very quickly after the delivery of multiple cells to designated areas.

In another study, the same group fabricated self-adjustable tubular scaffolds based on PCL and poly(lactide-*co*-glycolide) (PLGA) that can retain the shape of the scaffold during biodegradation.¹⁷⁸ PCL-PLGA multilayered tubes were fabricated using SIRM and microfluidic techniques. The inner PCL layer expands and the outer PLGA layer shrank to maintain the stability of tubular structure. The tubular structure was able to self-adjust and maintain the shape of the vessels even after degradation. This approach can be useful to design biodegradable tubular scaffolds that can self-adjust and maintain shape and architecture.

c. In vitro studies

Three types of cells, namely endothelial cells, smooth muscle cells and fibroblasts were patterned on the surface of SIRM. The cell-covered SIRM begins to roll up into a tube due to internal stress after one end of the SIRM being cut with a scalpel, and the cell sheet is layered as the tubular wall. To improve cell viability in long-term cultures, bottom layers were fabricated with pillars. When they roll up, they effectively separate the layers of the membrane, providing sufficient space for medium to get in and help keeping cells alive. Eventhough some cells are injured during rolling, most cells inside the tubes were found to be alive after three days.¹⁶³

The self-adjusting and shape memory properties of PCL-PLGA tubes were tested *in vitro* by incubating in cell culture [human umbilical vein endothelial cells (HUVECs), smooth muscle cells (SMCs), and fibroblasts], and compared to tubes made of either PCL or PLGA.¹⁷⁸ PCL-PLGA tubes showed loose inner cavities at the initial stages of incubation, and after 21 days they shrank, and all their layers merged into one layer. The inner diameter of PCL-PLGA tubes remained constant throughout the study, exhibiting the self-adjustment property in this environment, while PCL and PLGA tubes collapsed completely after 21 days due to the underlying shrinking and

swelling of the polymers (**Figure 4bi**). In the case of the composite (PCL-PLGA blend) PCL-PLGA layers are more stable because PCL component can hold the shape for longer duration without degradation of the PLGA layers. The difference in the degradation rates of PCL (slower) and PLGA (faster) was crucial for the maintenance of the durable mechanical support of architecture of the tubes. The endothelial cell responses and functions of shape-morphing scaffolds that have nanofibrous inner layer made of electrospun PCL/GelMA membrane were studied. This layer supported the formation of homogeneous endothelial cell attachment, the formation of biomimetic cell-scaffold interaction and cell-cell interaction, as compared to electrospun PCL membrane.¹⁶²

d. In vivo studies

In vivo conforming behavior of the shape changing and softening organic electronics was observed. An initially rigid, planar electronics with SMP coating was implanted under the skin of a rat. Over the first postoperative few hours, fluid uptake by SMP led to its plasticization, triggering softening (from more than 1 GPa to approximately 80 MPa). The initially planar devices softened and conformed to the biological environment and withstood 24 hours of fluid exposure and deformations associated with implantation in living tissue while maintaining the electrical properties without significant degradation (**Figure 4c**).¹⁶⁵

Before implantation, the twining electrode was flat making it convenient for handling and implantation. Following implantation next to the vagus nerve of rabbits, the twining process of the electrode was driven by 37°C saline. It underwent a self-climbing process similar to what is seen with twining plants. Accordingly, the twining electrode can conformally be in contact with the vagus nerve forming a good interface even under extreme deformation forces (**Figure 4d**).¹⁶⁶

The benefits of transformative electronics such as neural probes were witnessed after one month of implantation in the mouse brain. It was found that the device remained rigid at the temperature of the operating room but upon application in deep brain tissue it softens to match local tissue.¹⁷⁵ The transformative neural probe had both reduced lesion size and inflammatory glial responses as compared to non-transforming tungsten needles of the same dimensions, suggesting that the transformative approach is more amenable to deep tissue embedding. The devices remained intact and functional for at least six weeks following deep brain implantation.¹⁷⁵

In vivo studies conducted on rabbits demonstrated stability of the self-adjusting PCL-PLGA artificial blood vessel in maintaining shape and structure.¹⁷⁸ The artificial vascular replacement of the left carotid artery with PCL-PLGA tubes as artificial blood vessels and monitored the flow using Doppler ultrasound. After three months post-operatively, the implant allowed continuous blood flow with no significant change in the diameter of tubes, while the blood flow was obstructed in case of control PCL and PLGA tubes after three months due to their clogging. PCL and PLGA only tubes undergo sever structural damage leading to excessive tissue hyperplasia, whereas in the composite PCL-PLGA tubes, the shrinkages of PLGA-outer layer and well-maintained PCL inner layer contributed to structural maintenance of tubes and smooth transition from artificial blood vessel to fully remodeled native blood vessel.

e. Clinical studies

No clinical studies have been reported so far.

iii. Summary

Development of such well-controlled, complex structures that morph to predetermined shapes or self-change their mechanical properties have potential for applications in tissue engineering, drug delivery, sensing, soft robotics, as well as specific surgical procedures. Innovative techniques such as twinning electrodes can greatly reduce nerve injury caused by mechanical mismatch and surgical implantation.

Figure 4. Self-configuring/self-forming implants. **a)** Mechanisms. **i)** Illustration of stress-induced rolling membrane (SIRM) technology to fabricate three-dimensional (3D) patterns on tubes that contain cells (smooth muscle cells (SMCs), endothelial cells (ECs) and fibroblast layer), polycaprolactone (PCL) layer and poly(lactide-co-glycolide) (PLGA) layer in biomimetic fashion. **ii)** Shape memory mechanism, showing images of poly(octamethylene maleate anhydride) citrate scaffold before and after injection through glass capillary. **iii)** Self-climbing mechanism: Schematic presentation of peripheral nerves (left) and the formation of electrode-nerve interface, self-climbing of electrode from flattened state driven by the body temperature. **b)** Cell studies: **i)** Distribution of three types of cells (red: human umbilical vein endothelial cells, green: smooth muscle cells (SMCs); blue: fibroblast cells) from inside after rolling SIRM, indicating a similar pattern of blood vessels. **ii)** Magnification and side view of the tube. **iii)** Images of cell-laden PLGA-tube, PCL-PLGA and PCL tubes cultured in Dulbecco's modified eagle medium (DMEM) for different time period. PCL-PLGA maintained its regular shape for 21 days and the three layers of the PCL (one layer) and PLGA (two layers) merged into a single layer. PLGA and PCL tubes underwent significant transformation. PLGA tube shrank with its inner and outer diameter becoming smaller, while PCL tube gradually

swelled up leading to the collapse of tubular structure in both PCL and PLGA tubes. **iv)** Fluorescence image of POMAC scaffold containing live (green) and dead (red) rat cardiomyocytes after injection. POMAC scaffold exhibited autofluorescence in the red channels. Live cells filling the scaffold lattice are shown in green. **c)** *In vivo* studies: Bioluminescence imaging after subcutaneous implantation of surgically implanted (black arrow) and injected (green arrow) in rat cardiac tissues. The cells remained localized following subcutaneous injection, and no significant difference was observed between the two cardiac patches after 14 days of implantation. **d)** Application studies: Schematic diagram of vagus nerve stimulation (VNS) and implanted twining electrode on the vagus nerve on a rabbit model. Twining electrode with an inner diameter of 1 mm was implanted as it is equal to the diameter of vagus nerve of the rabbit. **Fig ai** and **biii** reproduced from ref.¹⁷⁸ with permission from Wiley-VCH, 2017. **Fig.bi** and **ii** reproduced with permission from ref. with permission from Wiley-VCH, 2012. **Fig. aii, iv** and **c** reproduced with permission from ref.¹⁷⁹ with permission from Nat. Mater., 2017. **Fig. aiii** and **d** reproduced with permission from ref.¹⁸⁰ with permission from Science 2019.

Table 2. A summary of the mechanisms and example applications of the **self-forming/self-reconfigurable** implants.

No.	Mechanism	How does the system work?	Applications	Comment	Ref.
1	Strain engineering	The release of a pre-stressed inorganic nanomembrane deposited at low temperatures onto a polymer sacrificial layer occurs after the removal of the sacrificial layer using a solvent. The membrane then rolls-up into a tube	Two-dimensional (2D) confined channels for the guidance of cell growth	A generic approach and different materials that have tunable diameters and lengths are used to produce tubular micro-/ nanostructures	¹⁶¹
		stress-induced rolling membrane (SIRM) is fabricated by bonding two elastic membranes together and the top membrane is stretched to produce stress. Different cell types are delivered and patterned on a 2D SIRM using microfluidic channels. SRIM is then released to roll up into a tube	Different cell types are used for the fabrication of multilayered tubular structures such as blood vessels	A strategy to produce tubular structures that have layered walls composed of different cell types. This allows precise control of cell location and orientation. The strategy enables 3D micro/nanofabrication by using initial patterning in 2D form with subsequent transformation into a 3D form	¹⁶³
2	Shape memory polymer	An elastic shape memory scaffold is developed by using a microfabricated lattice, which allows the engineered tissue to collapse during injection, and regain its original shape when placed at the desired location. Cell viability and tissue function are preserved during the process	Engineered organ-specific tissue patches for the liver, aorta and epicardium	A general method to fabricate flexible tissue patches for <i>in vivo</i> minimally invasive delivery	¹⁶⁴
		The shape-morphing scaffolds consist of a shaping layer composed of SMPs and a function layer. The shaping layer effectively achieved programmed deformation of the endothelial cell-laden	Small-diameter vascular grafts with improved endothelialization	By combining shape memory polymers (SMPs) and tissue engineering scaffolds, one can have a versatile method for achieving programmed deformation of cell-	¹⁶²

		constructs from temporary planar shapes to closed-hoop tubular shapes at the temperature (T_{trans}) of 37 °C		laden constructs into on-demand preplanned 3D structures. This will enable the engineering of complex cell-scaffold constructs that mimic native tissues and organs
		A three-dimensional (3D) twining electrode fabricated by using integrating stretchable mesh serpentine wires onto a flexible shape memory substrate. Its shape memory leads to recovery of its shape at the body temperature. Temporarily flat stiff twining electrode will self-climb onto nerves at the temperature of 37°C to form 3D flexible neural interfaces that exert minimal constraint on the nerves	Electrodes for peripheral nerve stimulation and recording	Proposed twining electrodes can reduce the risk of nerve injury that may occur due to mechanical and/or geometrical mismatches
		Fabrication of organic thin-film transistors on SMPs allows for the fabrication of electronics on a rigid substrate which can soften subsequently and change shape after heating above the T_{trans} of the SMPs (here 37°C in the body)	Implantable electronics with mechanical adaptability	These mechanically adaptable electronics have the potential to enable new means of creating intimate interfaces between body tissues and bioelectronics
3	Phase change metal	Temperature-triggered transition of soft-rigid phase of mechanically tunable electronics fabricated with gallium	Deep brain neural probe that remains rigid at the temperature of operating room and softens after deep brain injection	This approach has reduced lesion size and inflammatory glial responses, when compared to tungsten needles having the same dimensions, making it more amenable to deep tissue embedding
4	<i>In situ</i> forming implants based on solvent induced phase inversion	Water-insoluble biodegradable polymers dissolved in organic and water-miscible solvents. After injection, the organic solvent dissipates out and the water ingresses, resulting in the solidification of the polymers via phase separation	Tissue repair scaffolds, cell encapsulation, and bioengineering and drug delivery	These systems have several advantages that the need for critical temperature, presence of ions, and change in pH is not required

5	<i>In situ</i> forming implants based on photopolymerized crosslinking	Crosslinking of monomers with a minimum of two free radicals or cross-linkable polymers and a photo-initiator under light irritation	Tissue repair scaffolds, cell encapsulation, and bioengineering and drug delivery	These systems have the advantages of injectability facilitating minimal invasive surgery, while the limited penetration depth of light in tissue hinders their broad use	¹⁸²
6	Gelatin swelling	Microscale hollow tubules formed via curling of planar hydrogel materials driven by the difference in contractility and swelling ratio between its upper and lower layers	Biomimetic microvessels	A facile method to fabricate biomimetic microvessel scaffold with high accuracy, controllability, and handleability	¹⁶⁸
		A hydrogel-based actuated electrode array was designed using a thin-film electrode carrier and hydrogel-actuated shaft, consisting of silicon rubber and dispersed polyacrylamide hydrogel particles. These particles swell after implantation and induce shaft elongation, which leads to curling of electrode array across its axis	Cochlear implants	This approach is hoped to achieve both easy implantation and close contact with the nerve cells	¹⁷⁰
7	Stiffness varying via quick mineralization	Electromechanically active material is combined with compliant alginate gels. Cell-derived plasma membrane nanofragments (PMNFs) that can mineralize within 2 days are used to functionalize the gels, which promote the mineralization and stiffness in the gels that helps to design actuators of variable stiffness	Tools for bone repair or bone tissue engineering	PMNF-based biohybrid materials could simplify the process of building soft-robotic devices with multiple features (such as phase-changing capabilities, different morphology) that could be used in tissue engineering applications including robot assisted surgical procedures and morphing bioadhesives	¹⁷¹
8	Magnetic force	Magnets self-assemble into a predetermined macro configuration	Device for intestinal bypass creation	The technology enables the development of self-assembling magnets that can be used during endoscopic surgeries (for example dual-path bypass)	¹⁷⁶

2.2.7. Self-adaptation and expansion

Self-expandable implant can be defined as an implant with the capability to self-expand upon exposure to water or blood plasma. The implant can be crimped to a fraction of its original size and re-expanded when brought into contact with water or blood. Self-adaptable implants can possess the capability to adapt to certain situations, e.g. by exhibiting certain characteristics only when the situation is there, such as having an antibacterial activity that occurs only when the bacteria is present.

Self-expandable implants feature with intrinsic elasticity are useful for application in tubular structures.¹⁸³ Important tubular structures that need engineering include blood vessels,¹⁸⁴ gastrointestinal tract,¹⁸⁵ urogenital¹⁸⁶ and respiratory system.¹⁸⁷ Some implants e.g. tracheal scaffold have been successfully implanted in patients.¹⁸⁸ Biodegradable scaffolds or vessels are suitable candidates to replace defected blood vessels with coronary or peripheral bypass procedures. However, designing self-adaptive, self-expandable biodegradable tubular implants is a challenging task, considering various factors such as mechanical stability and durability. Recently, collagen based self-expandable (shape memory) implants have evolved as prime candidate, as they can be implanted using minimal invasive technique with improved endothelialization and possibility to incorporate bioactive components such as anticoagulants.¹⁸⁹

Self-adaptive implants are also important for fighting infections, as they will help to avoid the conventional methods of infection prevention and their side effect, e.g. implants employing as surface coating,^{190, 191} or functionalization^{190, 192} strategies. Self-adaptive implants were, therefore introduced to tackle infection, e.g. of the bone.¹⁹³ In this case, hydroxyapatite (HAp) was used as a sample material to establish the self-adaptive property, ethylenediamine-functionalized poly(glycidyl methacrylate) (PGED) brushes were grafted from HAp by surface initiated radical polymerization. Subsequently, an antibiotic, gentamicin sulfate (GS) was conjugated to PGED to produce self-adaptive and sustainable antibacterial HAp implant (**Figure 5a**).

i. Mechanism

Self-expansion property can be achieved by employing self-memory materials. For example, an implant with shape memory was produced by using carbodiimide cross-linking in combination with compression technique¹⁹⁴ Star-shaped tubular scaffolds, which expanded upon increase of luminal pressure and collapsed after the pressure release, was produced.¹⁸³ These tubular structures mainly function to transport fluids in the body. The implant had the ability to self-expand from crimped state to a tubular shape, like self-expandable stent which are used in vascular disease treatment. Multiple steps were involved in the fabrication of collagen implant: (a) formation of tubular scaffolds by swelling type I collagen in acetic acid, followed by casting, molding, freezing and lyophilization process; (b) compression of tubular scaffolds between aluminum objects to develop thin films (step. 2); (c) Carbodiimide crosslinking reaction to stabilize the tubular structure, followed by washing with disodium phosphate (Na_2HPO_4); and (d) crosslinked scaffolds were placed on metal guidewire, crimped using automated radical compressor machine and air.

ii. Studies

a. Concept studies

The implants based on type 1 collagen have shown the ability to self-expand from a crimped stated to tubular shape which can be potentially used for vascular disease treatment.

b. Material level studies

No studies have been identified

c. In vitro studies

Cytocompatibility studies on self-expandable collagen scaffolds performed using human endothelial cells and human smooth muscle cells showed that cells were present on both luminal side as well as outside of the scaffold, however, no penetration was observed in the interior regions of the scaffolds.¹⁸³ *In vitro* studies indicated that HAp-GS3 (GS3 indicates 2.5 wt.% GS contents), with highest drug loading exhibited high antibacterial ability against *E. coli* and *S. aureus*, even after five repeated tests, while pristine HAp displayed no antibacterial ability.¹⁹³ Furthermore, the porous structure of HAp provided ample space for bacterial proliferation. The results proved the sustainable antibacterial ability of Self-adaptable HAp-GS material.

d. In vivo studies

No animal experiments on the self-expansion/self-adaption properties have been performed so far.

e. Clinical studies

No clinical trials have been conducted so far.

iii. Summary

The technological development of collagen-based self-expandable implants have provided a way to construct implants that can mimic dynamicity of native tissues such as seen with blood vessels, urogenital and gastrointestinal tract. These self-expandable implants can be crimped to a fraction of its original size and re-expands upon exposure to fluids such as blood, which make them suitable for application using minimally invasive procedures.¹⁹⁵

The development of self-adaptive implants with sustainable response provides an alternative novel approach for addressing problems such as implant-associated infection. No reports of material studies were identified. *In vitro* studies demonstrated antibacterial ability against *E. coli* and *S. aureus*. *In vivo* studies demonstrated antibacterial responses and self-adaptive drug release. Future, there implant may have potential for use as a biological vascular implant.

2.2.8. Self-awareness

Self-awareness can be defined as implant capability to sense and monitor its orientation, location and status, when it is implanted in the body.^{16, 17} Self-awareness is very important for an implant to be able to “feel” surroundings and make appropriate adjustment and response. To achieve self-awareness, many capabilities should, however, be possessed by the implant. These include sensing, self-powering, and self-monitoring.¹⁶ So far, this could be achieved by the assembly of meta-tribomaterial sensors and nanogenerators. Self-aware implants have been developed with the vision of being a part of personalized implants and aid in detecting and reducing complications in future.

ii. Mechanism

Self-awareness can be achieved by using composite metamaterials known as self-aware composite mechanical metamaterials (SCMMs) that can transform mechanical metamaterials into

nanogenerators and active sensing tools. Self-aware materials can sense and self-program, using their constituent components. In addition, they can also be self-powering. The system is an integration of self-recovering snapping microstructures consisting of topologically different triboelectric materials that can provide the functions of the tribomaterial system. Self-aware implants are structure dominated, hence based on the target application, their geometry (shape, size and stiffness) can be tuned by modifying number and deformation sequence of auxetic cells, integrated microstructures and layers material.

Recently, this mechanism was studied to produce self-aware spinal fusion cage implants (**Figure 5a**).¹⁶ The implant integrated conductive and non-conductive triboelectric layers, semi-circular shaped curved elements that can provide support, as well as elastic snapping before and after deformation. During spinal movement, an electrical output is generated by the contact of conducting and non-conductive layers of cage, with voltage signal is proportional to the forces applied to the structure. The mechanism is based on a *relative healing* approach, where the voltage signal generated in the cage is compared with the signals in previous stage, considered as the *reference baseline*. The implant thus can serve as a sensor and energy harvesting mechanism.

Compression loading tests showed that the rings of a synthetic spinal model and fusion cage become stiffer, they tend to carry more weight which reduces the strains inside the cage, resulting in lower voltage. The decrease in voltage in turn indicates progress in the healing process. The proposed self-aware technology is definitely a new path for monitoring the healing process. Further, innovative self-aware implants can be fabricated using a wide range of metals such as Ti, Au), bioresorbable polymers such as polylactide (PLA), PLGA, and bioresorbable metallic (magnesium) materials with triboelectric charging.

Another strategy was adopted to develop a self-aware artificial auditory neuronal part of a cochlear implant, that reduces power consumption by a spiking neural network (SNN).¹⁹⁶ The SNN-based auditory system possess self-aware sensing capability for sound signals. The system comprised a triboelectric nanogenerator (TENG) as the auditory sensor, and bi-stable resistor (biristor) as the spiking neuron (**Figure 5c**). When the sound pressure was applied to TENG, it generated alternating current (AC) and transferred to biristor neuron as input, subsequently, biristor neuron converted current input to voltage as output for SNN. The system was tested using a musical instrument, for detecting sound pitch with measured spiking characteristics and it was able to distinguish two different sound pitches originating from a piano.

These functionalities are achieved via integrating nano energy harvesting TENG mechanisms and mechanical metamaterial design paradigms. The multifunctional metamaterial systems will act as TENG capable of generating electrical signals when stimulated by the application of mechanical excitations. The electrical signal can then be used either for sensing of the applied force or it can be stored for empowering sensors and embedded electronics.

ii. Studies (Explanatory examples)

a. Concept/design

Self-aware implants are still in the very early stage of development where the concept is being tested. For **example**, investigators have developed a SCMM-based self-sensing and self-powering cardiovascular stent and cardiac shock absorber.¹⁷ The concept of “self-aware composite

mechanical metamaterial” was proposed by Barri *et al.*^{197, 198} to enable the creation of a new generation of multifunctional and metamaterial implantable devices that can respond to their environment, power themselves, and self-monitor their condition.

b. Material studies

Designing self-aware implants depends on many parameters that include the type of material, thermal-mechanical stability, and cost effectiveness. Although the use of natural materials is appealing; however, because of their limitations in energy conversion and integration in implant, and mechanical properties to sustain load, synthetic materials are used for the fabrication of self-aware implants. Synthetic metamaterials can be multifunctional and can be used to develop composite self-aware structures that can convert metamaterials into nanogenerators and sensing devices.¹⁷

Composite mechanical meta-tribomaterial systems can also be developed using parallel snapping curved segments exhibiting mechanical self-recovery behavior.¹⁷ To develop this system, a metamaterial was fabricated using thick horizontal and vertical elements and thin curved parts. The 2D structure of snapping composite metamaterial consisted of two conductive layers embedded with thicker dielectric layer (**Figure 5b**). Uniaxial loading between 15 and 45 N applied on 3D printed metamaterial structure showed a large deformation due to the discrepancy between the snapping and supporting components. However, when the force was applied vertically to the center of curved beams, the semi-circular shaped segment shells were mechanically deformed (**Figure 5b**). When the SCMM concept was applied to design shock absorbers, a continuous measurement of applied forces and energy harvesting was seen from the external mechanical excitations. Although SCMM concept has some innovative edge for designing self-aware energy harvesting metamaterials, the actual implementation of this concept still needs to be explored further to optimize the set-up, durability and robustness of material and viability for commercial fabrication.

The feasibility of SCMM mechanism for designing multifunctional systems such as cardiovascular stents and shock absorbers was demonstrated.¹⁷ To achieve this, a layered meta-tribomaterial system consisting of integrated microstructures of topologically different triboelectric materials to act as a TENG and sensing system were used¹⁷. The conductive layer was made of carbon black while the dielectric layers were made of PLA and polyurethane. The deformation mode of integrated microstructure of the implant generates contact electrification when the two surfaces of the SCMM structure undergo periodic changes due to mechanical excitation. The two layers of the system act as the conductive and dielectric layers which collect positive and negative charges. It is presumed that when the SCMM structure is uploaded, the charge remains on the surface of the dielectric layer which forms a static electric field and a potential difference between the conductive layers. The snapping SCMM structures undergo periodic deformations under compress loading which results in contact electrification between conductive and non-conductive surfaces. By unloading the structure, a potential difference occurs between the conductive layers. Consequently, more contact takes place between the conductive and dielectric layers, which generates high electrical output. The generated electrical output signals provide active sensing, while the generated electrical energy can be harvested and stored to empower sensors and electronics of the implant. Moreover, the metamaterial implant with TENG mechanism provides good mechanical stability of the implant.

Inspired by the leopard tortoise which has curvature to position itself towards center of mass and strong upper shell architecture that anchors the self-orientation towards upright position, an ingestible self-orientating millimeter-scale applicator (SOMA) was developed.¹⁹⁹ It comprised a mono-monostatic body that can independently position itself in the gastrointestinal tract and insert drug-loaded milliposts into the stomach, and then it travels down to exit (**Figure 5d**). Low density PCL and high-density stainless steel were used to produce the low center mass needed for SOMA for the self-orientation of the device. A stainless-steel spring was used as a power source considering the limited space and force generation along the single axis.

c. In vitro studies

In vitro studies demonstrated self-awareness of the self-orientation SOMA implant.¹⁹⁹ When the implant was placed on a tilt shaker running at 50 rpm with excursion of 15°, the SOMA did not tilt more than a single degree, and oriented itself quickly from 30° and a 135° angle.

d. In vivo studies

Experiments in swine stomachs (*ex vivo*) and fasted (*in vivo*) swine showed that the mass distribution of SOMA did not affect implant orientation in the stomach, and SOMA oriented 100 % of trials, when compared to virgin PCL-based device which oriented only 50 % of the time. Micro-computed tomography (micro-CT) images from *in situ* and *ex vivo* experiments demonstrated the insertion of the implant milliposts into the stomach (**Figure 5e**). The milliposts were inserted into swine tissue by seven mm when a force of 1N was applied, and delivered about 0.3 mg of insulin. No signs of damage to the stomach were seen via an endoscopy performed one-week post-injection. Histological studies confirmed that the device can deliver milliposts without injuring other muscular layers of the stomach.

e. Clinical experiments/trials/routine use

Up to our knowledge, no clinical studies have been reported so far.

iii. Summary

Self-aware implants come as an innovative concept which provides a next generation of implants, although experiments conducted are limited to spinal implants using spine and human cadaver spine models, cardiovascular stents and cardiac shock absorbers. Self-orientation millimeter scale applicator (SOMA) that autonomously inserts drug loaded millipost into the stomach, can be considered as one step forward in achieving self-orientation, yet there are certain hurdles that need to be addressed. For instance, the limited deliverable dose and the appropriate insertion technique, as we do not have proper control over the depth and width of the millipore penetration, which need to be addressed in future research. Although studies have shown the orientation of SOMA in some fluids, more experiments need to be conducted using fluids with different viscosities, and under varying conditions such as temperature, time, internal pressure etc. *In vitro* studies have so far been conducted only to test the self-awareness of SOMA implant, and more experiments need to be conducted on other self-aware implants. More *in vivo* studies on large animals are required before clinical can be pursued. Other aspects such as mechanical stability and biocompatibility properties need investigation. Studies of economic aspects, and scale-up should be carried out.

Figure 5. Self-aware implants. An illustration of a nanogenerator interbody fusion cage implanted during spinal fusion surgery, showing: **(a)** components of self-aware cage implant, **(b)** design of three-dimensionally (3D) printed self-aware composite mechanical metamaterial (SCMM) at the original and deformed states under cyclic loading, **(c)** self-aware artificial auditory system consisting of triboelectric nanogenerator (TENG) and biristor neuron which can generate spikes for neural processing with the spiking neural network (SNN), **(d)** Illustration of self-orientating millimeter-scale applicator (SOMA) showing its orientation in the stomach towards the gastric wall, and **(e)** Image of the SOMA device showing the self-orientation of SOMA device in a porcine stomach, following its administration and agitation of the abdomen using 180° rotations and 30° tilts. Figures adapted with permission: **a**, ref.¹⁶, Wiley-VCH; **b**, ref.¹⁷, Elsevier; **c**, ref.²⁰⁰, Elsevier. Figures reproduced with permission from: **d** and **e**. ref.¹⁹⁹ with permission from AAAS.

2.2.9. Self-actuation

Self-actuation property of an implant is the action taken by the implant, e.g. the release of loaded cargo following exposure to a specific trigger, without the need for external control. Self-actuation could also include changes in the implant shape, mechanical properties, position, electromagnetic properties, biomaterial surface status or other actions. Instead of externally aided actuation, self-actuation can be a better strategy that can be developed and integrated in future autonomous implants.²⁰¹ The purpose of having a self-actuation implant is to start an action without the need for external instruction, but only to specific triggers. For example, a self-actuating implant would release an antimicrobial agent in response to infection.

i. Mechanism

The actuation takes place after changes in implant properties triggered by specific stimulus, e.g. low pH in the surrounding environment to undergo changes in its properties including chemical activity, porosity and mechanical structure. that lead to the release of its cargo, e.g. release of antibiotics in response to a developing peri-implant infection²⁰² (**Figure 6ai, ii and iii**). Some of these stimuli result from the interaction between the implant surface and cell membranes,²⁰² triggering physicochemical reactions on the interface of implant-tissue.

In one example, the transfer of electrons between the coating material (HAp/molybdenum sulfide, HAp/MoS₂) and bacteria that may come in contact with the implant leads to self-activation of the antibacterial included in the coating, i.e. (HAp/MoS₂).²¹ In another surface mechanism based on a superhydrophobic star-shaped response platform, it was demonstrated superior anti-adhesion self-actuation in experiments with *E. coli* and *S. aureus* generated by a self-actuated Cassie-Baxter wetting state, which creates an extreme reduced adhesion to bacteria.²⁰³ Upon taking up water, hydrogels can generate a difference in the hydrostatic pressure in certain devices that can have a self-bending property. For example, self-bending electrodes in cochlear implants, can be applied to induce electrode contact with nerve cells of the inner ear.²⁰⁴ Hydrogels can also be used to develop self-folded devices for the engineering of functional cardiac tissue.²⁰⁵ Varying biomaterial stiffness can be used to stimulate self-regeneration of tissues.⁷ Moreover, changes in the implant architecture can be achieved by the incorporation of fungi into implants induces due to the expansion of fungi promoted by favorable environmental conditions.¹⁹

ii. Studies

a. Concept/design studies

Similarly, a multifunctional hydrogel coating on phthalazinone (PPENK) was proposed for biomedical implants. The multifunctional gelatin containing black phosphorus promoted self-activating antibacterial properties under photothermal mediation associated with osteogenic features by activation of locally controlled release of loaded doxorubicin and generation of reactive O₂ species (ROS) to combat bacteria.²⁰⁶ Targeting combats the strain *S. aureus*, a PCN-222 metal organic framework incorporated with bismuth nanoparticles was proposed as a rapid therapy for infected-wound. The physio-chemical status of this biomimetic nanozyme is capable to induce a difference in the charge potential of the bacterial membrane promoting self-driven electron transfer on the interface which is suggested to disturbs and impairs the bacteria metabolism, suggesting potential for the design of self-antibacterial biomaterials.²⁰⁷ To control foreign body response and extend the efficacy of drug-releasing devices, a dynamic actuation approach was pursued by using

synergistic soft robotic abilities: an intermittent actuation and a controlled actuation (**Figure 6b and c**)²⁰⁸.

Self-actuating pre-programmed materials that can vary their stiffness actuators to influence tissue healing and regeneration, e.g. of the bone, can be useful biomedical implants. To demonstrate this, a hybrid device was developed. The device changes from soft to stiff conditions material by bone mineralization process in its internal layer (made of polypyrrole). The hybrid device is produced of alginate functionalized with cell-derived plasma membrane nanofragments which promoted this biological process.²⁷

b. Material studies

The mechanotherapeutic function applying cycling stimulation for five minutes every 12 hours to preserve long drug-release of the system was tested in a human cadaver model by minimally invasive percutaneous implantation at the *transversus abdominis* muscles of a soft actuatable platform with drug-release features showing easy manipulation in a human-scaled device, which is promising for clinical use, e.g. in the treatment of fibrosis and type 1 diabetes.²⁰⁸

c. In vitro studies

The antibacterial efficacy of the self-activating antibacterial HAp/MoS₂ coating of Ti6Al4V (Ti6) implants against *S. aureus* and *E. coli* was examined *in vitro* (**Figure 6d**).²¹ It leads to a reduction in the count of methicillin-resistant *S. aureus* (MRSA), which was attributed to MoS₂.²⁰⁹ The combination of printed hydrogels incorporated with living organisms (fungal mycelium) led to the development of self-cleaning 3D scaffolds when supported by nutrients and water¹⁸. The growth of these fungi in the hydrogel expands its layers and also changes the shape of the biomaterial.

d. In vivo studies

Experiments performed in rats showed that *S. aureus*-contaminated HAp/MoS₂-Ti6-coated implants had reduced bacteria colonization as compared to non-coated implants, following 14 days of implantation.²¹ There were also less neutrophils around the coated implants as compared to non-coated ones (**Figure 6d and e**). A self-aligning intraocular pressure measuring device that employs gold-coated neodymium-iron boron (NdFeB) micro-magnet sleeves over fibers, which generate a strong magnetic field that enables the fibers to maintain the alignment,^{210,211} was tested in rabbit and it was found to provide stable measurements at constant hydrostatic pressure in the eyes of rabbits.²¹²

e. Clinical

No clinical studies on self-actuating implants have been reported so far.

iv. Summary

Although the self-actuating systems were developed in various forms, the technology is still in its early infancy and studies remain limited to lab tests, with a couple used *in vitro* cell culture, one used human cadaver implantation at the abdominal muscles investigating clinical translatability and a couple using animal experiments. Technology remains to be properly evaluated both *in vitro* and *in vivo* for biocompatibility and functionality and validated using comparable existing methods if such conventional therapies are used at all. Because of the complexity of the system, multidisciplinary teams are required. A close eye should be kept on this emerging technology.

Figure 6. Self-actuating/activating implants. a) Mechanisms of self-actuation. **a-i)** Self-actuating implant to treat contaminated tissue. **a-ii)** activation of drug-release from the self-actuating implant triggered by changes in the local pH, photo-exposition or magnetic field. **a-iii)** Tissue regeneration by self-antibacterial releasing device. **b)** Examples of designs and self-activation. **b-i)** Drug-release by a self-actuating implant demonstrated using methylene blue. **b-ii)** Photoacoustic pictures demonstrating the release of drug (red area) from a self-actuating platform implanted in a rodent model, showing the subcutaneous transference of the drug from the implant drug reservoir to the tissue pockets of the animal. **b-iii)** Mechanism of drug-release and self-actuation presented by the developed system. The implanted platform self-actuates a compression on the above membrane releasing the drug from the under membrane to the tissues caused by foreign body response underlying the platform. Legend: RR: rapid release. **c)** Application studies (*in vitro* and *in vivo*). **c-i)** *In vitro* application of implant surfaces with self-antibacterial properties. Self-activated antibacterial effect caused by HA/MoS₂-Ti6 coating reducing *E. coli* and *S. aureus* survival demonstrated by qualitative images (microscopies – LIVE/DEAD and SEM techniques) and quantitative colony count (graph). **c-ii)** *In vivo* application of implants having self-antibacterial surfaces in rat bones. Quality of bone integration in contaminated or non-contaminated environment showed by radiographs and micro-CT exhibited better bone regeneration and bacterial combat compared to implants without the innovative surface. Figure a was created using Biorender®. Figures (b, and c) reproduced and adapted from ref²⁰⁸ and ref,²¹ with permission from Springer Nature.

2.2.10. Self-powering

A self-powering implant is an implant that gets its power independent of batteries or external supply of energy. Although there has been advances in developing implantable batteries²¹³ there remains problems with continuous power supply for integrated systems with more complex systems that require more power²¹⁴. In addition, conventional lithium-ion batteries may contain toxic substances in both electrodes and electrolytes. For long-term service, the batteries need also to be surgically replaced periodically, which imposes a huge economic and health burden. External powering using wire was developed but it carries the risk of developing infection. Alternatively, external wireless powering was explored by using inductive power transfer,²¹⁵ radiofrequency irradiation,²¹⁶ acoustic power transfer,²¹⁷ optical power transfer,²¹⁸ magnetoelectric power transfer,²¹⁹ and capacitive power transfer.^{220 221 222, 223} However, this strategy is associated with challenges related to performance,²²⁴ tissue absorption,^{225, 226} receivers required to capture sufficient power,²²⁷ etc. Therefore, extensive research has been carried out into designing self-powered implants in the past few years,^{16, 32, 228} to obviate problems associated with batteries and external powering. Self-powering obviates the need for implantable batteries of external power supply, and thus avoids adverse effects that are associated with powering.

i. Mechanism

Self-powering can be achieved via harvesting energy, e.g. from the surroundings, such as energy generated by movement, flow, heat, or chemical changes (**Figure 7**). Harvesting energy generated by body motion includes leveraging muscle contraction/relaxation (mechanical energy), blood circulation (hydraulic energy). The chemical energy resulting from salts/glucose etc. can also be converted into electrical energy.²²⁹ Based on the characteristics of energy forms, appropriate energy harvesting systems such as TENG, piezoelectric nanogenerator (PENG), pyroelectric nanogenerator (PyNG), hygroelectric nanogenerator (HEG) and

electromagnetic power devices are utilized for the conversion.^{223, 230 231} For example, mechanical energy resulting from the movement of the heart, lung and diaphragm can be harvested using PENG or TENG to provide self-powering of the implant.^{232, 233} The energy harvesting ability of TENG relies on triboelectrification and electrostatic induction effects between two friction layers.²³⁴ Based on the working mode and linkage of external circuits, they are divided into four types, namely vertical contact separation mode, lateral sliding mode, single electrode mode, and freestanding triboelectric layer mode. The vertical contact separation type is widely used for the self-powered implant systems.²³⁵ Other mechanisms such as electromagnetic induction²³⁶ and electromagnetic generators (EMGs) have also been suggested for energy harvesting. Recently, the use of flexible NdFeB magnets was shown to convert the mechanical energy associated with finger movement into electrical energy and power wearable sensors.²³⁶ Piezoelectric nanogenerators (PENG) is another potential energy conversion device that utilizes the piezoelectric effect.²³⁷ When an external force is exerted on piezoelectric nanomaterials, the internal electric voltage difference generates tension on materials through electric dipole moments.

iii. Studies

a. Concept studies

A concept of self-powered smart knee implant which generates power by the frictional sliding of two ridge-shaped surfaces when a person walks implant was presented.²⁰ The sliding occurs as a result of transfers of electrons from one surface to another and provides self-powered charge to the implant. There are other concepts that have been reported and they discuss implant functions associated with self-powered sensors,²³⁸ actuator,²³⁹ human powered devices²⁴⁰ and others.³² In these concept implantable micro/nano systems as self-powering units that could operate for long time within body without the need of replacing batteries, resulting in harvesting biomechanical energies from body itself.

b. Material studies

The first piezoelectric nanogenerator was based on zinc oxide (ZnO) nanowires (NW), which converted mechanical energy into electrical energy.²³⁷ The mechanism of power generation was dependent on the coupling of piezoelectric and semiconducting properties of ZnO. The nanogenerator was able to harvest energy from the environment that can be developed into a self-powering unit. The ZnO nanowires were grown on aluminum oxide (Al₂O₃) substrate, using Au particles as a catalyst, by vapor-liquid-solid (VLS) process.²⁴¹ NW arrays were grown on atomic force microscope tip in contact mode. The coupling of piezoelectric and semiconducting properties in ZnO created a strain field and charge separation across NW as a result of its bending. The rectifying characteristics of the potential energy barrier formed between the metal tip and the NW led to power generation with efficiency of 17 to 30 % for a cycle of resonance. The study revealed that by changing the size of NW array, power generated can drive small single nanotube-based devices. Once the resonance of a NW array can be achieved to output the piezoelectric-converted power generated in each cycle of vibration, a significantly strong power source becomes possible for self-powering implants. In 2010, Li *et al.* first developed an implanted flexible PENG using a two-ends bonded ZnO nanowires.²⁴² Later, self-powering cardiac pacemaker was produced by harvesting the natural energy of heartbeats with rigid PENG made of an elastic skeleton of polyethylene terephthalate (PET) sheet and two piezoelectric composites consists of a piezoelectric layer, beryllium-bronze foil, and Cr/Au electrodes was reported²⁴³. More recently, a battery-free heart pacemaker that is powered by a flexible PENG was developed. The PENG is comprised of

composite nanofibers of poly(vinylidene fluoride) (PVDF) and a hybrid nanofiller made of zinc oxide (ZnO) and reduced graphene oxide (rGO).²⁴⁴

A self-powered electrical stimulator for inducing bone formation and healing was built using TENG and flexible interdigitated electrode using PET as substrate and packed by PDMS.²⁴⁵ In another study, a self-rechargeable cardiac pacemaker system with *in vivo* TENG (I-TENG) that works based on the body motion and gravity was developed.²⁴⁶ The gravity was constructed using amine-functionalized poly(vinyl alcohol) and perfluoroalkoxy as triboelectric material. The maximum volume power density was $4.9 \mu\text{WRMS}/\text{cm}^3$ (at $\sim 10 \text{ M}\Omega$) and harvested around 144 mW in preclinical animal experiments.

Bulky nanogenerators have limited utility due to their incongruent contact with the surface of organs such as brain, lung, and heart thus being unsuitable to harvest the minute movements of internal organs, a flexible nanogenerator is more suitable for energy harvest on organ surface. Such a flexible triboelectric active sensor (I-TEAS) was fabricated employing a multilayer thin-film structure composed of triboelectric layers, electrodes, and spacers that were encapsulated with multilayer biocompatible materials, which provided real-time and continuous monitoring functions for various physiological and pathological signs by sensing the biomechanical motion of intracorporeal organs.²⁴⁷ Another study reported a self-powered flexible and implantable electrical stimulator consisting of a flexible TENG consists of two friction layers of aluminum (Al) and polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) films, a rectifier and a flexible interdigitated electrode, which could be driven by the daily movement to meddle bone homeostasis.²⁴⁵

In a recent study, wearable self-powered wound dressing was fabricated by integrating thermocatalyst bismuth telluride (Bi_2Te_3) and mechanical energy harvesting layer of chitosan coated carbon fiber fabrics (CFFs), that can be triggered by diverse stimuli (mechanical motion and temperature gradient) and can provide on-demand treatment for both normal and infected wounds.²³⁰ The dressing structure was composed of two CFF-based electrodes coated with chitosan hydrogel on the exterior side. CFFs served as substrate and electrode layers to maintain conformal contact with wound, while chitosan hydrogel was used as the external layer because of its biocompatibility and ability to retain moisture. The dressing was also triggered to generate local electric field around the wound by connecting the integrated electrodes to an arch shaped TENG.

In a recent study, biodegradable supercapacitor implant was developed from molybdenum oxide (MoO_x) flakes, which were grown *in situ* on water soluble Mo foil and sodium alginate gel (Alg-Na) electrolyte using electrochemical oxidation approach (**Figure 7b**).²⁴⁸ Anodized MoO_x flakes formed by applying alternating voltage between 0 to 1 V is firmly adhered to Mo foil current collection, which derives low contact resistance and alleviates the exfoliation of active materials during the electrochemical reactions. During continuous electrochemical cycling, the interconnected MoO_x flakes forms cracks which are filled with Alg-Na gel that facilitates contact between electrolyte ions and MoO_x flakes. Moreover, MoO_x flakes had layered structure with many surface and edge defects which provided abundant storage sites for anchoring extraneous ions during the electrochemical reaction process and promoted charge transfer. The unique MoO_x flake-based electrode displayed high electrochemical performance. This supercapacitor was shown to have high areal capacitance of 112.5 mF cm^{-2} at 1 mA cm^{-2} and excellent energy density ($15.64 \mu\text{Wh cm}^{-2}$)/high power density (2.53 mW cm^{-2}). The life span of supercapacitor

implants can be varied to extend from a few days to a few weeks. The supercapacitor can be degraded through a series of metabolic and hydrolytic reactions, and the resulting by-products can be absorbed by the body without any adverse long-term effects as they have shown in rats.

A recent study reported the development of self-powered wireless bioresorbable implant for programmed drug delivery that has a drug reservoir which acts as a battery, to provide power needed to open the gates of the device.²⁴⁹ The device was built with electrochemically active metal foil which serves as an anode, and electropositive metal foil which serves as a cathode (**Figure 7c**). The two foils are interconnected by a conductive paste. Another connection joins the cathode to collector terminals of phototransistors. When phototransistor is exposed to external light it accelerates the corrosion of anode to open the underlying reservoir and release the drug. The implantation forms a battery with collection of electrochemical cells, where biofluid serves as a common electrolyte. The drug reservoir itself acts as a battery, to self-power the implant and provide sufficient power needed to open the gate.

c. In vitro studies

In an *in vitro* study using osteoblast progenitor cells, self-powered stimulator made from TENG and interdigitated electrodes of PET and PDMS was shown to promote cell adhesion, proliferation and differentiation²⁴⁵ The cell attachment and spreading started immediately after seeding. It increased the number of attached progenitor cells by 72.76% after three hours of stimulation and increased the total spreading area by 78.37% after one hour of stimulation. Furthermore, cell proliferation was enhanced by 23.82% after three days of stimulation and the differentiation by 28.2% after 12 days of stimulation (**Figure 7d**). Bacterial adhesion was effectively inhibited, the number of bacteria was reduced and the live/dead bacteria ratio in forming and mature biofilms was reduced by using a self-powered anodized titanium implant with TENG that was built to provide long-term effective negatively charged implant surface²⁵⁰. The negatively charged implant surface also promoted the spreading and differentiation of osteoblast progenitor cells, without adverse side effects.

In vitro studies on self-powered wound dressing were assessed against *E. coli* and *S. aureus* through a standard plate counting method and live or dead bacterial assays.²³⁰ The results indicated a temperature gradient-dependent inhibition of bacterial growth. When the temperature gradient was increased from 0° to 15°C, the survival rate of *E. coli* decreased from 100 to 16 %. The wound dressing was further examined to determine the correlation between the amount of H₂O₂ generated and the antibacterial performance. When the temperature difference was 15 °C, functionalized Bi₂Te₃ NPs generated about 4.4 μm H₂O₂ which decreased the survival rates of *E. coli* and *S. aureus* to 12.7 and 18.7 in 30 min.

d. In vivo studies

In vivo studies conducted on adult mongrel (dog) showed that I-TENG behaved independently and charged capacitors based on the physical movements.²⁴⁶ For example, when the animal was active, the capacitor voltage has rapidly increased, and when it was calm, the system load consumed energy with storage voltage became saturated or decreased. The I-TENG charged capacitors even from small movements when the animal was asleep. It was considered appropriate for body-implantable medical materials. In another study, flexible triboelectric active sensor (I-TEAS) was implanted in pigs to monitor the physiological and pathological signs by sensing the biomechanical

motion of intracorporeal organs.²⁴⁷ In responding to the heartbeat and breathing, an electric output with a short-circuit current of $\sim 4\mu\text{A}$ was generated, exhibiting a self-powering capability of system, without the need of any battery. Moreover, the integration of nanostructured triboelectric layers and the encapsulated materials enabled the I-TEAS to detect tiny changes of motions of surrounding organs. The rate of heartbeats and respiration was precisely monitored, with no reduction in sensor properties. In another study, PENG was implanted on the heart surface of a rat and powered by stretching releasing repeatedly as the heart expands and contracts. The results indicate that output signals were almost synchronized with the heartbeats.²⁴²

PENG was implanted on the heart surface of a rat and powered by stretch-relaxation repeatedly as the heart expands and contracts. The results indicate that output signals were almost synchronized with the heartbeats.²⁴² When the rigid PENG was fixed at apex of pericardial sac where the motion amplitude of the heart is largest compared to other sites, the maximal output open-circuit voltage (V_{oc}) and short-circuit current (I_{sc}) of 20 V and 15 μA , were obtained.²⁴³ The PENG-powered pacemaker produced a pacing pulse with an amplitude of ~ 2.5 V and the pulse width of ~ 2 ms at the preset rate of 80 beats per minute, which was identical to the output of the pacemaker powered by an external battery. The heart could be continuously paced by the PENG-powered modern full-function pacemaker. In another study, after the implantation of the PENG on the lateral wall of left ventricles of dogs, it was found that the PENG implantation has brought no burden to the heart. It produced voltage, synchronous with the heartbeat. The PENG has harvested as high as 0.487 μJ electrical energy from every heartbeat, which is larger than the commercial pacemaker pacing threshold. The *in vivo* energy harvested by the PENG has powered a commercial pacemaker, generating pacing pulses at the preset parameters.²⁴⁴

In vivo degradation evaluation of an absorbable supercapacitor implant was studied in a rat.²⁴⁸ The implant was fully resorbed by rat through metabolism after a month, with leakage of MoOx flakes, electrolyte from the broken implant, which was noticed after three months and complete dissolution after six months. No inflammatory reaction was observed during the degradation process. In a recent study, wearable self-powered wound dressing was fabricated by integrating TENG and thermocatalyst bismuth telluride (Bi_2Te_3), that can be triggered by diverse stimuli (mechanical motion and temperature gradient).²⁵¹ When dressing was done in the infected wound, the thermocatalyst produced H_2O_2 for *in situ* bacterial eradication, while TENG generated electrical stimulation to promote wound healing. *In vivo* studies conducted on mice showed that wearable self-powered dressing, in the presence of an electric field (EF) generated by the TENG, fibroblast proliferation and migration were enhanced by ~ 2.1 and ~ 3.2 fold.²³⁰ After twelve days, TENG treated wounds were completely recovered ($< 11\%$), while the relative wound closure for control was still $\sim 31\%$ (**Figure 7e**). The pulsed DC output from the TENG directed the cells towards the center of wound from the edges, resulting in progressive reduction in wound area to 71.59 % along the direction of electric field.

In vivo studies of self-powered electrical simulator were conducted by implanting stimulator on the surface of femur of rats (**Figure 7f**).²⁴⁵ The output measurements were conducted by pulling the rats leg using a liner motor, the mechanical energy generated by the leg movement was converted to electrical energy by TENG. The energy was stored in the capacitor to drive stimulator periodically (**Figure 7f**). It was observed that TENG identified the short-circuit current and the transferred charge were reached around 1 nA. Studies were also conducted on rats to study the

self-powered device that triggers drug release based on light-controlled mechanism.²⁴⁹ The drug reservoir containing lidocaine was placed adjacent to the injured nerve. When the light passed, the drug was released from the reservoir which induced a decrease in grip strength and paw withdrawal threshold of right hind limb which confirmed the physiological effect of the lidocaine release from the device. Although the work highlighted the biocompatibility and bioresorbability of the device, the use of non-resorbable phototransistors, optical filters, the amount of drug and number of reservoirs that can be equipped with implant, and the wavelength that can trigger the release are challenges that still need to be addressed.

e. Clinical studies

No clinical studies have been reported so far.

iii. Summary

Advances in current self-powered implants enabled the development of diagnostic and therapeutic BIMEs that allowed *in vivo* sensing and tissue stimulation over long periods time relevant to clinical standards. Flexible configurations of Self powering systems rely of the conversion of endogenous energy in the body such as motion, flow, heat, or chemical changes. Advances in biodegradable implantable medical electronics (BIMEs) such as pacemakers and neurostimulators, have been achieved over the past few years due to the advancement in materials development. Nonetheless, one of the standing challenges is degradation of these self-powered implants in the body. The degradation rates of these implants are not well controlled; they lack mechanical strength and induce inflammation reactions in the acidic medium. Another challenge is to predict the exact degradation process *in vivo*, as it is influenced by the implant design and its location in the tissues. Biodegradable metals based on Mg, iron (Fe) and zinc (Zn) have been extensively studied for developing biodegradable metallic implants. There is also a need to develop self-powering implants with hybrid energy harvesters or systems that are capable of scavenging energy from multiple sources simultaneously, thereby counterbalancing any limitations caused from single units. Efforts should be focused on enhancing the lifetime of self-powered implants. Although current self-powered implants have achieved significant progress in integrating with biological systems, they are still in their infancy. The challenges include lifespan of system, degradability, how to achieve long-term coupling and biosafety to comply with normal organ function, how to achieve and volumetric energy density, and how to effectively integrate with other functional components. Multidisciplinary collaboration among scientists, engineers, and clinicians is required. In addition, more large-animal studies should be performed to enable clinical applications at a later stage.

Figure 7. Self-powering. **a)** Power sources by harvesting energy generated by body movement, flow, heat, or chemical changes and the types of energy harvesting systems such as triboelectric nanogenerator (TENG), piezoelectric nanogenerator (PENG), pyroelectric nanogenerator (PyNG) and hydroelectric nanogenerator (HEG) devices utilized for the conversion. **b)** Preparation of fully biodegradable supercapacitor implant by a sandwich construction of Mo foil (current collector), MoO_x flakes and Alg-Na gel electrolyte. **c)** Schematic of self-powered programmable release of drugs, and diagram showing the metal gate structure that serves as the anode of battery system, and their light-controlled electrochemical corrosion lead to controlled opening of drug reservoirs, therefore providing a basis for programmable release of drugs. The phototransistor decreases its electrical resistance and thus short circuits the electrochemical cell formed by the anode and cathode with surround biofluids as the electrolyte. The process initiates corrosion of the gate and opening of the underlying drug reservoir. Optical filters placed on top of the phototransistors create a wavelength selective response. **d)** Example of *in vitro* study: Fluorescence images show enhanced proliferation of fibroblasts cells electrically stimulated by TENG for three days. **e)** Example of *in vivo* study: Self-powered treatment for healing of *S. aureus*-infected wound. Images showing the wound contraction areas. TENG groups showed ~ 32% relative wound closure area, which was about three times lower than that in normal wound after day 12. **f)** Example of *in vivo* study: Flexible TENG implanted on the surface of femur region of rat the output measurement process by the daily movement of rats by pulling the leg of rat using a linear motor. Figure (b) reproduced from ref.²⁵² with permission from Science, 2021 c) reproduced from ref.²⁴⁹ with permission from PNAS, 2023, d and e) reproduced from ref.²⁵¹ with permission from Science, 2023 f) reproduced from ref.²⁴⁵ with permission from Elsevier, 2019.

2.2.11. Self-oxygenation

Self-oxygenated implant is an implant with capability of generating O_2 by incorporation of O_2 -generating materials.²⁵³⁻²⁵⁵ Cells require a continuous supply of O_2 to survive. To keep cellular implants alive is a challenging task, because angiogenesis takes a week or two to form vessels that

can supply these implants after their implantation in the body, a time which is too long for cells to wait. Therefore, the development of self-oxygenated implants is appealing. The concept of self-oxygenated implants or tissue constructs is new, which is based on self-oxygenated materials that can potentially store and supply O₂ on demand (**Figure 8**). It was also found that O₂ gradients can potentially guide stem cell fate toward osteogenesis.²⁵⁶ Materials such as self-oxygenated bioinks for 3D bioprinting have been developed to fabricate tissue constructs^{257, 258} and injectable oxygenated hydrogels for cardio-protective procedures.²⁵⁹

Tissue engineering approach employs mammalian cells to regenerate the structure. However, cells mostly die after transplantation because of the lack of blood supply.²⁶⁰ Approaches that employ vascularized tissues, microvascular anastomosis, angiogenic growth factors, endothelial cells have limited success.^{261, 262} Recently generation of O₂ by materials included in the constructs has been explored.^{258, 263} It aims to provide cells with O₂ while angiogenesis is taking place, With the hope to have impact on the outcome of cellular implants in the body (**Figure 3a-iv**).

i. Mechanism

Self-oxygenation can be achieved by incorporating O₂-generating materials such as calcium peroxide (CPO),²⁶⁴ hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂),^{265, 266} perfluorocarbon compounds,^{267, 268} magnesium peroxide (MgO₂)²⁶⁹ and sodium percarbonate (Na₂CO₃),²⁷⁰⁻²⁷² that can store and supply O₂ on demand. CPO is most commonly used material, which generates O₂ via the intermediate formation of hydrogen peroxide, as presented in the following equation:²⁷³

The lower concentration of hydrogen peroxide can lead to the formation of free radicals that can lead to cell death.^{274, 275} To protect cell damage various antioxidants and scavenging enzymes such as catalase, superoxide dismutase and glutathione peroxidase are used that hydrolyze peroxides into water and O₂.^{276, 277} Recently, hydrophobic O₂-generators (HOGs) have been developed, which can readily integrate within engineered tissues (**Figure 8a**).²⁷⁸ There have been concerns that oxygenation may inhibit angiogenesis which is stimulated by hypoxia induced factor. However, in a study that delivered O₂-generating particles to the heart in mice, it was found that endothelial were rather enhanced, and improved vascularization led to an increase in cardiomyocyte survival by ~ 30 %.²⁵⁹ Thus, regulating O₂ levels within implants is important not only for cell metabolism but also for the development of blood vessels and ECM components.²⁷⁹

ii. Studies

a. Concept studies

Studies on the concept demonstrated the possibility to locally generate O₂ by using peroxides (liquid and solid),^{280, 281} or cyanobacteria.²⁸²

b. Material Studies

The oxygenating ability of injectable tyramine-conjugated alginate and silk fibroin encapsulated with oxygen-releasing microparticles (TSF/OMP) hydrogels was tested using O₂ release experiments by suspending the gels in culture media and saline, and measuring O₂ release for 14 days.²⁵⁹ The incorporation of OMPs in hydrogel significantly altered the O₂ release kinetics. The composite hydrogels displayed a steady O₂ release for two weeks, followed by a drop of 3-4 % by the sixth day. The drop was due to the entrapment of the released gaseous O₂ in the hydrogel

network which was not detected by the O₂ sensor probe. TSF/OMP hydrogels maintained a steady O₂ level of <5%, which is thought to be suitable for alleviating anoxic injury.

In a recent study, self-oxygenated injectable hydrogel composed of tyramine (TA), alginate and stromal cell-derived factor-1 alpha (SDF) and encapsulated O₂-releasing microparticles (OMPs) for sustained release of SDF and O₂ (**Figure 8b**).²⁵⁹ Alg was conjugated by TA via chemically crosslink with tyrosine in the silk fibroin (SF) to obtain hybrid TA-conjugated Alg and SF (henceforth TSF) hydrogel. SF was introduced to improve the elasticity and toughness of alginate hydrogels. To achieve injectability, enzymatic crosslinking was performed using horseradish peroxidase (HRP) and hydrogen peroxide to crosslink TA-conjugated Alg, SF and SDF *in-situ* after injection. This helps chemical crosslink of TA-Alg and SF hydrogels to tissues and aromatic amino groups of proteins to the ECM. In another approach, OMPs were incorporated into GelMA containing silica nanoparticles under different O₂ deficient conditions.²⁸³ In this study, amphiphilic GelMA chains were coated on the surface of hydrophobic OMPs while hydrophilic amino acid of GelMA chains interacted with water phase, to produce homogeneous dispersion of OMPs in GelMA hydrogels. CPO incorporating hydrophobic PCL microparticles were able to generate O₂ and they can be used as a part of self-oxygenating implants (**Figure 8c and d**).²⁷⁸

c. *In vitro* studies

Injectable TSF/OMF hydrogel were assessed for their effect on the survival, proliferation of HUVECs and endothelialization in ~0.5 % O₂ (anoxic) and ~5% O₂ (normoxic) environment.²⁵⁹ The results from 14 days' study revealed that hydrogels maintained > 90% cell viability under both conditions. Further, the metabolic activity after 14 days of culture showed higher Ki-67 expression than pristine hydrogels cultured under both anoxic and normoxic conditions. It was concluded that TSF/OMP hydrogel induced higher endothelial cell proliferation.

It was also found that O₂ gradients can potentially guide stem cell fate toward osteogenesis.²⁵⁶ *In vitro* studies were performed on bulk mRNA sequence analysis of nanocomposite hydrogels containing OMP at different concentrations.²⁸³ hMSCs were encapsulated in GelMA hydrogels containing OMP (0.25%). The hydrogels were cultured under normoxia /anoxia in an osteogenic differentiation medium for 28 days. A global analysis showed that gene expression under anoxia was increased towards osteogenesis for OMP group at 14 and 28 days, indicating that modulation of local O₂ tension using self-oxygenating hydrogels which can potentially govern the differentiation of hMSCs towards osteogenesis of engineered tissue constructs/implants for bone defects (**Figure 9e**). In another study, hMSCs encapsulated in GelMA/OMP hydrogels showed a higher rate of cell survival and proliferation as compared to GelMA/ silica nanoparticles (SNPs) at two weeks.²⁸³ The analysis of gene expression for osteogenesis revealed that, under anoxia condition, there was an upregulation of genes in the OMP constructs, such as bone morphogenetic protein 6 (BMP6), activating transcription factor 4 (ATF4), catenin beta 1 encoding gene (CTNNB1), hairy and enhancer of split-1 (HES1) and DExD-Box helicase 1 (DDX21), indicating the promotion of osteogenesis by self-oxygenated hydrogels.

In one study, GelMA hydrogel incorporated with calcium peroxide improved the function of human cardiac cells cultured under hypoxic condition.²⁸⁴ OMPs incorporated into GelMA hydrogels that have with silica nanoparticles, were shown to decline in their viability from around 90 to below 80% under normoxia (human mesenchymal stem cells (hMSCs)).²⁸³ *In vitro* studies were done to investigate the ability of HOGs for protecting cells from cytotoxic effects of

generated hydrogen peroxide.²⁷⁸ Self-oxygenated tissues were produced by incorporating hMSCs in GelMA hydrogels containing different concentrations of CPO or HOGs. Under normoxic conditions, the addition of CPO led to massive cell death even at low concentrations (2.5 %), whereas self-oxygenated tissues based on HOGs demonstrated a minor decrease in cell survival event at high concentration (10%), which proved cytoprotective nature of these materials. Under anoxic culture conditions, these self-oxygenated tissues based on HOG-GelMA formulations enabled ~80% cell viability for 12 days, even at low concentrations (2.5%). Cell survival rate of was identical in both conditions which indicated that HOGs effectively avoided cell death throughout the volume of self-oxygenated tissues. O₂ generated by cyanobacteria,²⁸² was shown to eradicate biofilm formation by *Streptococcus gordonii*, *P. gingivalis*, *Fusobacterium nucleatum* and *Porphyromonas gingivalis*. Similarly, self-supplying H₂O₂ modified nanozyme-loaded hydrogel was shown to eradicate biofilm formation by *Enterococcus faecalis* and *Streptococcus sanguis*.²⁸⁵

d. In vivo studies

Studies on rat acute myocardial infarction (MI) showed that TSF/OMP hydrogels led to reduction in fibrotic areas.²⁵⁹ Furthermore, they induced higher number of myocardial vessel formation compared to pristine hydrogel. began to degrade after two to three weeks post-implantation. Although the expression of HIF-1 α , which transcribes genes important in angiogenesis, was found to decrease in animals treated with TSF/OMP hydrogel, lower cell death was observed due to oxygenation (**Figure 8d-i**). It is evident that O₂ is also crucial for maintaining healthy endothelia and achieving neovascularization. Qualitative analysis showed that angiogenesis was promoted, and vascular networks were more organized in the hearts treated with TSF/OMP or TSF/OMP/SDF hydrogels. In another study, self-oxygenated (GelMA/OMP) hydrogels implanted on the back of rats were found to undergo slow biodegradation and resulted in increased cell proliferation, CD31+ cells vascularization, and vessel diameter (**Figure 8d-ii**).²⁸³ The use of self-oxygenated injectable hydrogel that encapsulated O₂-releasing microparticles and used for sustained release of SDF and O₂ at the MI sites in rats was found to prevent hypoxia-induced cell death better than OMPs or SDF alone.²⁵⁹ Although studies have been carried out to investigate the effect of O₂-generating materials on the functional behavior of implant, such as hypoxia,^{286,287} osteochondral bone defects and other disease conditions,^{288,289} their actual functioning inside the body is not yet investigated. Engineering tissue implant with the complex geometries of vascular networks and achieving complete integration with host tissues is a big challenge, since it not only enables the delivery of O₂, but also enhances nutrient supply and helps in the removal of metabolic waste.

In vivo experiments in rats showed that HOG mediated self-oxygenated tissues composed of GelMA hydrogels containing 2 x 10⁶ cells, hMSCs and HOGs, displayed a healthy looking pink appearance with complex patterns which resembled like vascular structure while control group appeared dark color (**Figure 8d-iii**)²⁷⁸ seven days post-implantation. Human nuclear antigen staining (HNA) proved that hMSCs of self-oxygenated implant remained *in situ*, predominantly around the vessels (**Figure 8d-iii**). In addition, the engineered tissues also contributed to the integration with host tissues [(human nuclear antigen (HNA)] and CD31+, suggesting in growth of host vascular system.

In another study, O₂ releasing BCP scaffold incorporated with CPO was implanted in rabbits to enhance the bone repair *in vivo*. Bone regeneration was significantly improved in the CPO-coated

scaffolds compared to bare ones. After six months post-surgery, new bone formation was evident around the periphery of the scaffolds and along the native bone.²⁹⁰

e. Clinical

No clinical studies up to our knowledge.

iii. Summary

Inadequate supply of O₂ after implantation may lead to constraints on cells, including inadequate angiogenesis leading to improper function of the implant. Advanced technologies such as 3D printing and microfluidic chips may help us to improve implants by controlling and uniform O₂ supply in future implants. HOGs are promising approaches to developing clinically sized tissues for regenerative applications.²⁷⁸ Self-oxygenated implants are evolving as a new type of implant that can be designed into tissue constructs, complex vessel networks, hydrogel, or scaffolds that can possibly solve the O₂ deficiencies. In the future, there is also a need to integrate self-regulating components into the engineered implant for a controlled on-demand supply of O₂. Moreover, using self-oxygenating materials that can be triggered by changes in local pH can be useful to the implant. Self-oxygenated devices are a futuristic design of autonomous implants, expected to advance in the coming years. Currently, available tissue constructs have many limitations, viz., management of O₂ supply to the target cells/tissues, proper O₂-generating sources, assembling with an implant, and proper degradation, which require further research and testing through large animal models to get substantial understanding that can help us to take next steps for clinical applications. Integration of sensor technology with implants could help monitor the internal condition. Regulatory approval of self-oxygenating implants is another challenge, and approval and commercialization may take longer than other implants.

Figure 8. Self-oxygenating implants. Concept of self-oxygenating implant. **a) (i)** Illustration showing self-oxygenating materials and the release of oxygen (O_2) on GelMA nanocomposite hydrogel. Mechanisms. **(ii)** Schematic illustration of reactions underlying O_2 generation via CPO hydrolysis and H_2O_2 decomposition by catalase in hydrophobic O_2 generating microparticles encapsulated with CPO. **b)** Material studies: Core-shell structure of O_2 release microsphere and O_2 release kinetics (a) PLGA shell, (b) PVA/ H_2O_2 core, (c) combined core-shell structure and (d) SEM image of microsphere²⁶⁶. **c)** Cell studies: Studies on HUVECs cells showing enhanced cell survival with the use of Ki67 staining and CD31 expression on TSF gel in Normoxia and Anoxia conditions after 14 days of culture, **d)** *In vivo* studies: i) TSF based therapeutic hydrogel implanted at the infarct area. Representative image of HIF-1 α staining from the left ventricular ischemic region 3 weeks post injection²⁵⁹. (ii) Microphotographs of histological sections of GelMA and 0.25 % OMP stained for neovascularization (CD31) of hydrogels showed a slow degradation and lesser neovascularization in the GelMA constructs even after 3 weeks post implantation²⁸³. (iii) Bright-field images of explants taken seven days post-implantation. Micrographs of 5 micrometer thin midsagittal section of implants that were stained with HNA/CRP. Semi-quantitative image analysis of core and outside of stained tissue sections of HNA staining showed that hMSCs of self-oxygenated tissues remained present in the implant and were located around the vessels²⁷⁸. Figure **b** reproduced from ref. ²⁶⁶ with permission from Nature, 2018; **c** and **d-i** reproduced from ref. ²⁵⁹ with permission from Wiley-VCH, 2024, **d-ii** reproduced from ref. ²⁸³ with permission from Elsevier, 2023, and **d-iii** reproduced from ref. ²⁷⁸ with permission from Wiley-VCH, 2021.

2.2.12. Self-destruction

Self-destructive implant is an implant with the capability to degrade autonomously when exposed to triggers. Self-destructive biomaterials can degrade upon exposure to external stimuli such as chemical cues²⁹¹⁻²⁹³ and optical excitations,²⁹⁴ which initiate a self-disintegration process that drives the cleavage of labile linkages proximal to the core polymer networks in the biomaterial. These materials can be helpful in controlled release applications, where their degradation leads to the release of prodrugs²⁹⁵ and enzymes^{296, 297} entrapped inside the biomaterial network.

i. Mechanism

Self-destruction can be achieved by force triggering a polymer using DNA-linked hydrogel. In a recent study, DNA hairpins were used as the force sensors for structural transition, and RNA guided endonuclease (CRISPR Cas 12a) was used as a selective degradation system to activate DNA hairpins under mechanical strain (**Figure 9 ai-iii**).²⁹⁸

ii. Studies

a. Concept studies

So far, no studies have been identified based on this concept of self-destructive materials.

b. Material studies

Self-destruction of hydrogels was studied by introducing Cas12a on hydrogels synthesized using DNA hairpins (DNA HP) with different GC content and doping gold nanoparticles (AuNP).²⁹⁸ The hydrogel crosslinked with ssDNA and GC showed complete self-destruction in 30 min under zero external forces, indicating thermal breathing of DNA HPs contributed to the destruction of hydrogels (**Figure 9b-i**). When both Cas12a and external forces were applied, self-destruction of the hydrogel occurred after three hours of incubation and the release of AuNP. It was predicted that force-induced self-destruction happened due to the opening of DNA HP crosslinkers inside hydrogel, which triggered Cas12a breakdown of DNA crosslinker, ultimately leading to hydrogel self-destruction. Rheological studies carried out on the material following the application of stress and Cas12a enzyme showed that the decay of the self-destructive material was initially slow, but it suddenly dropped to zero after a certain period. It was predicted that initial relaxation was caused by hydrogel relaxation behavior, while the sudden drop in stress was due to the self-destruction of the gel (**Figure 9b-ii-iv**).

c. In vitro studies

No studies have been reported so far.

d. In vivo studies

No studies have been reported so far.

e. Clinical studies

No studies have been reported so far.

iii. Summary

Self-destruction is an important concept activated upon exposure to triggering stimuli, which can be useful in applications such as the release of their lead. The application of external forces triggers

degradation, e.g., DNA crosslinkers and cleavage of the network in hydrogel and, finally, its self-destruction. Self-destructing materials can also be used for sensing and other applications. So far, *in vitro* studies have not been reported. No preclinical animal or clinical studies. It is expected that self-destructive materials will soon have a place similar to other stimuli-responsive materials in clinical applications, such as the treatment of infection, cancer, inflammatory diseases, and others.

Figure 9. **a)** illustration of mechanism of self-destructing hydrogel. **(i)** hydrogel consisting of DNA crosslinks and tetra PEG **(ii)** forces-induced opening of DNA HP sites, which leads to CRISPR-Cas12a cleavage of the DNA. The black and blue arrows represent the external forces and the forces of the polymer backbone, respectively, and **(iii)** self-destruction of hydrogel due to the cleavage of ssDNA crosslinks. **b)** Material studies: **(i)** Synthesis of self-destructive hydrogel by crosslinking tPEG DBCO and bisazide- modified DNA. **(ii)** Image of hydrogel under different conditions. **(a)** hydrogel prepared without Cas12a under external force. **(b)** with Cas 12a without external force and **(c)** with Cas12 and continuous external force application. The photographs were taken at $t=0$ and 3 h of continuous external force. **(iii)** Graph showing the degradation of crosslinked hydrogels by the tPEG-N₃, ssDNA and 80 % GC HP. **(iv)** Plots showing the stress relaxation of hydrogels without Cas12a enzyme **(a)** and with Cas12a enzyme **(b)**. In the presence of Cas12a enzyme, the stress showed a sudden decrease depending on the GC content of HP. ssDNA crosslinked hydrogel degraded at ~50 min, and DNA HP degraded at 65 min. The hydrogels with 100% GC HP showed the most resistance to Cas12a activity and degraded around 80 min. Figure a-e Reproduced from ref. ²⁹⁸ with permission from Wiley-VCH, 2023.

3. ASSEMBLY OF DIFFERENT PROPERTIES INTO THE TARGET IMPLANT

3.1. General view

Integrating various self-performing implants discussed in different sections above can guide us to develop an autonomous implant that can effectively detect, sense, monitor, self-heal, and manage itself for a longer duration of time without any problems or the need for external intervention. The aim is to develop an implant that can mimic as much as possible native tissues in terms of functional and structural connections with the surroundings, for e.g., (a) self-awareness, healing, orientation/reconfiguration, regeneration, and communication. This will require integrating multiple components to achieve these capabilities. The implant will provide not only therapeutic benefits but also diagnostic capabilities.

Prototypes based on two-component systems, e.g. spine fusion cage model,¹⁶ cardiovascular stents¹⁷ and shock absorbers¹⁷ with self-sensing and self-powering functionalities have been developed and underwent testing, e.g. for self-sensing and self-powering implant.^{16, 17} Experimental and theoretical analysis were conducted on the developed models to quantitatively study the mechanical and electrical behaviors. In this context, a self-sensing and self-powering spinal fusion cage model was tested on both synthetic spine and human cadaver spine models to assess the fusion process and energy harvesting from mechanical excitations¹⁶. Although, mechanical and electrical performance were tested, but they still need to be customized for individual patients based on the clinical needs and anatomical structure. So far, *no vitro* and *in vivo* studies have been reported for these implants. Considering various innovations in different implants, we have divided implants into the following categories:

3.2. First generation

The first generation of automated implants can be defined as the implants with one specific property, e.g. self-healing, self-sensing, self-actuation or self-powering property. The aim of using the first generation of autonomous implants is to advance technology beyond the current state of the art of implants used in the clinic, i.e. having some smart property that enables, e.g. self-awareness, self-healing, sensing, actuation or communication. Examples include *in vitro* and *in-*

in vivo experiments of developing self-healing implants for the treatment of brain injury,^{103, 299} and Parkinson's disease, self-healing hydrogels for the treatment of diabetic wounds,^{300, 301} self-powered knee implants³⁰² and cardiac pacemaker,³⁰³ self-sensing implants for collecting data on bone healing and monitoring bone-implant interface.^{22, 304}

For the fabrication of the 1st generation of autonomous implants, we need: (a) appropriate biocompatible materials, (b) appropriate design, which should consider all biomechanical and biological factors that are required for the proper function, e.g. a self-aware implant spine cage requires high-resolution imaging and computer modeling for its design that enables matching bone structure and joint mechanics. Other techniques such as 3D computer-aided design (CAD) models^{305, 306} will help to fabricate intricate structures with restricted geometries. Various types of nanosized structures such as metal-organic frameworks, nanorods, nanocubes, quantum dots and nanopillars, that are used in the fabrication of implants are very important to be considered.^{307, 308} (c) creating complex geometries. Techniques such as 3D printing allow us to create customized implants that can fit individual patient anatomy and needs. (e) fabrication protocol needs to be developed that can be used for commercial purposes, e.g. the fabrication of a self-healing hydrogel can be improved by developing new theories on self-healing mechanisms.

For testing of autonomous implants viz., self-aware implants, mechanical tests should be performed to evaluate the static and dynamic fatigue properties using standard protocols such as American Society of Testing and Materials (ASTM) and different spine models. The mechanical properties have to be tuned based on the requirements. The nanogenerators which are used in the self-powered implants need to be monitored and the lifetime of these nanogenerators have to be studied in animal models. We need advanced techniques to study the self-aware implants when placed in an animal model. The application of artificial intelligence (AI) is a useful tool in characterization of implants using complex algorithms to generate useful output.^{309 310} To optimize the biomechanical models, *in vivo* studies will be required, b) performing preclinical testing of new implants c) monitoring the process after insertion of implant. For example, for self-healing implants, *in situ* evaluation through quantitative techniques, and non-destructiveness is required³¹¹. Advanced morphological techniques, multi-scale characterization will be need for better understanding of atomic and molecular scale observations, that can be converted into quantitative and numerical information.³¹² Advanced numerical healing kinetics could help design self-healing materials that allows to design the appropriate materials suitable for self-healing implants.³¹³

Scale-up will be required to develop small scale energy generators for self-aware and self-powering implants with the ability to provide sufficient and continuous energy supply to the implants. Many analyses such as technical and design considerations, and manufacturing process have to be carried out before scale-up and manufacture of the first generation implants. Implant function and durability has to be proved in short- and long-term *in vivo* studies, including the use of specific models for target applications. Besides functionality, the biocompatibility of the implant and of byproducts has to be demonstrated before moving to clinical studies. So far, no clinical studies on the first-generation autonomous implants were reported. This largely due to the lack of long-term and comprehensive *in vivo* studies which should be pursued in the course of developing this implant generation.

According to EU Medical Device Regulations, an orthopedic implant (e.g. Self-powered knee implants) belong to class II, the highest risk class.³¹⁴ Currently, it would be challenging for these autonomous implants to undergo the same Food and Drug Administration (FDA) or EU approvals, as the overall process takes years to complete and involves extensive clinical trials before approval is granted. Regulatory approval of the autonomous implant involves biocompatibility testing which determines if the implant is safe while in the body (such as ruptures, infections or complications), effectiveness, manufacturing standards etc.

Currently, the first generation of autonomous implants has been well developed and it has proved to work in many *in vitro* and *in vivo* studies. However, long-term, large animal studies, and specific application models are still missing, e.g. for self healing,^{100, 103} self powered²⁵¹ and self-regenerating implants.¹⁴⁷ These are needed to advance to clinical applications. Self-powered implants (TENGs driven by low-frequency mechanical sources) are under consideration to enhance the dielectric constants of triboelectric material. There is growing focus on bioresorbable TENG^{315, 316} needle sized injectable TENG³¹⁷ and self-powered wireless monitoring systems. On the other side of the scale, no *in-vitro* and *in-vivo* studies have been reported on self-aware implants. The experiments conducted so far are still at its concept level, where the advances in nanogenerators and metamaterials could play a crucial role and guide us to develop next generation multifunctional implant that could be used by clinicians to achieve better surgical outcomes. Other types of the first generation autonomous implants are being studied *in vitro* and in experimental animals.

Self-powered implants still require surgical removal for recharging energy storage, thereby imposing physical and psychological strain on patients. To improve the system, we need more self-powered implants that can potentially self-recharge or extended operation time inside the body and reduce the risk of surgery, such as self-rechargeable cardiac pacemakers²⁴⁶ Self-powered implant integrated with wireless control of programmed drug delivery will be the next step,²⁴⁹ and it could provide solution for long-term powering and monitoring the physiological condition of the patient. Therapeutic approaches for designing self-healing implants for brain diseases are advancing, however need further improvement when translating into humans. The implants should mimic the mechanical properties of brain tissue while maintaining other functionalities including adhesion, conductivity, anti-inflammatory, antioxidant and hemostatic properties. When implanted, the cells or drugs should be able to effectively migrate and interact with brain tissues and initiate healing process. The overall mechanism needs a deeper understanding.

3.3. Second generation

The second generation of autonomous implants are those that combine two autonomy characteristics, e.g., spinal fusion implants with self-sensing and self-powering features¹⁶. Combining more than one self-performing function will enhance the effectiveness of the implant and reduce risks and get us one step closer to the realization of the vision of autonomous implants that can mimic native tissues. The fabrication of second-generation implants requires special design and sometimes different fabrication techniques to include two characteristics in one implant. For example, a self-aware and self-powering implants will require the use of meta-tribomaterial technology with multiple layers of triboelectric auxetic microstructures with multi-stable or self-recovering snapping segments to achieve self-awareness property,¹⁷ and nanogenerators to achieve self-powering. The system relies on rational design of implants to embed advanced functionalities into the matrix. By manipulating the geometrical design, the

implant can be transferred into a sensor and nano-generator. Integration of multiple circuit boards, powering sources into the implant, scalability and availability of biocompatible raw materials for the fabrication of these implants is another challenge.

This generation of implants needs to undergo specific testing to demonstrate that they have two functions, which do not interfere with each other. For example, self-sensing and self-powering based spinal fusion cage implant and cardiovascular stents and shock absorbers need to be tested in small and large animals before proceeding towards clinical applications. Process, materials and design of the implants have to be optimized by interconnecting various parameters that can create the basis for the scale-up of 2nd generation implants. Mass production of materials will be needed for designing the implants. Recent advances in nanocomposite materials,³¹⁸ broad range of designs have been created and technologies that allow engineers to identify appropriate materials and mass production of the same. Although self-aware implant via meta-tribomaterial technology is a step-forward, the development of robust and long-term performance evaluation of these implants *in vivo* is required. Clinical trials need to be conducted using these implants before they can be practically brought into regular use.

Appropriate studies and detailed reports of studies on materials properties, behavior, their biocompatibility and durability are required. In the European Union (EU), these implants and devices are regulated by Active Implantable medical Devices Directive (AIMDD), the Medical Devices Directive (MDD) and In Vitro Diagnostic Medical Device Directive (IVDMDD).³¹⁹ In the US, FDA regulates implants for their safety and effectiveness. Federal regulations (such as code of Federal Regulations) must be fulfilled for the Center for Medical Devices and Radiological Health (CDRH) to approve implants in the US. Although technology is still at the concept level, self-aware orthopedic 2nd generation implants having both diagnostic and energy harvesting capabilities, they have potential to help in the assessment of bone healing process around them.¹⁶
³²⁰ The fabrication of actual models still needs to be made, and *in vitro* and *in vivo* studies carried out.

3.3. Third generation

The third-generation implants can be defined as implants formed by combining three or more autonomy characteristics. To integrate multiple self-functioning implants into one autonomous implant, which is the next big step closer to native tissues. Fabrication of 3rd generation can be considered a futuristic implant with multi-features, adaptable and tunability, based on specific needs. A combination of automation and flexibility in design will be a crucial aspect. We need hybrid material and technology that combines natural and synthetic materials in appropriate ratios, and each material provides its functionality. The assembly of individual self-units, e.g., self-powering, self-actuating, and self-healing implants into a single unit requires technological development (including powering units, nanogenerators), material development (biomaterials, nanocomposites) and method development (2D, 3D, and 4D). The current need is to improve the fabrication method to a higher level of control and accuracy with automatic fabrication methods while retaining a clinically relevant production rate. Integrating wireless data logging technology to generate fully self-powered systems will be another option.³²¹

This generation of implants is still in the preliminary stages of development, and only proof-of-concept tests were carried out.¹⁶ Studies of these implants need to define the properties of implant

having three autonomy features, e.g. in case of self-sensing, self-powering and monitoring implant, efficiency of self-aware implants in assessing fusion process of the spine and energy harvesting from mechanical excitations need to be defined. Furthermore, *in vivo* studies of this 3rd generation of autonomous implants are required. Self-aware implants can be considered as a third generation due to multiple properties they have such as self-sensing, self-monitoring and self-powering through energy harvesting.

For scale-up, e.g. of self-powering, self-monitor and self-sensing implants, the use of advanced fabrication technologies such as 3D printing may help the design and scaleup customized implants.³²² Furthermore, the use of AI may also be helpful in this process. Prior to clinical studies, large animals should be performed to define biocompatibility, safety, effectiveness, and durability. An appropriate power management module for long-term operation of nanogenerators used in implants, sensors with sensing capabilities should be optimized. In the example of self-aware implants, optimal mechanical and electrical performance of the implants should be proved¹⁶. Similar to other generations (1st and 2nd), tests to demonstrate safety and efficacy are required. The complexity of the third generation imposes more challenges on the type and number of tests to generate data required to approve safety and efficacy. In addition, models required to demonstrate the function of the 3rd generation will be more demanding.

The multifunctional metamaterials (3rd generation), which act as their own sensors, recording and generate their own power have already been developed¹⁶, moreover, the nanogenerator eliminates the need for a separate powering source. A tiny chip is embedded in the self-aware implants which records data about the pressure in the spinal cage, as an indicator of the healing process. No *in vitro*, *in vivo* or clinical studies have been reported so far.

3.4. Forth generation (tissue-mimic)

The fourth-generation automated implant can be defined as the implant with multiple features. These implants incorporate many capabilities to make them so close in mimicking native tissues (tissue like mimics). This type of implant that combines four automation properties does not currently exist, but it is expected to be the next step in the path of development of automated implants.

4. APPLICATIONS

Autonomous implants discussed above can be investigated for various applications, such as bone regeneration,²⁷ bone healing process,²⁴⁵ wound healing¹⁴⁷ and drug delivery.^{100, 103, 202} Besides applications tested so far in animals, there are also many other potential applications (**Table 3**).

Table 3. Applications of different autonomous implants and their clinical outcomes.

Tissue/organ	Implant	Actual application	Potential application	Ref.
Bone	Self-aware implant	<u>Concept level:</u> Interbody fusion cage prototype for detecting bone healing process using voltage signals via built-in contact-electrification mechanisms	Diagnosing bone healing process using voltage signals	

		Test: synthetic spine models	
	Self-powered implant	Self-powered stimulator- <i>in vivo</i> studies	Bone fracture and bone remodeling after bone transplantation ²⁴⁵
	Self-actuating implant	<u>Concept level:</u> Bioinduced variable stiffness actuators with pre-programmed shapes that can change properties and grow own bone	Treatment of bone fracture and bone regeneration ²⁷
	Self-activating implant	Self-activating coating for drug-release of molecules (<i>in vitro</i> studies).	Antibacterial dental implants and improved bone regeneration. ²⁰²
	Self-activating implant	Self-activating multifunctional hydrogel coating. (<i>in vitro</i> and <i>in vivo</i> studies)	Anti-tumor therapy, antibacterial surface for implants and improve bone regeneration ²⁰⁶
CVS	Self-aware implant	<u>Concept level-</u> meta-tribomaterial nanogenerators with energy harvesting and sensing functionalities	Designing artificial materials for cardiovascular stents and shock absorbers ⁶⁶
	Self-healing	Scaffolds- <i>In vitro and in vivo studies</i>	Wound healing, neural regeneration in the brain after ischemic stroke ^{100, 103}
ENT (cochlear implant)	Self-aware implant	<u>Concept Level:</u> Spiking neural network	Auditory system
	Self-healing	Hydrogels, <i>ex vivo</i> studies	Voice recovery ²⁸
Gastrointestinal tract	Self-orienting system	<i>In vivo</i> studies-	Drug release capsule ¹⁹⁹
	Self-regeneration	Engineered living hydrogels, <i>in vitro, in vivo</i> studies	Mucosal wound healing ¹⁴⁷
Tissue engineering and wound healing	Self-forming implants	Stress-induced rolling membranes, <i>in vitro</i> studies,	Artificial blood vessels and tubular structure in and tissue
	Self-powered	Self-powered dressing, <i>in vitro</i> and <i>in vivo</i> studies	Wound healing, promising therapeutic platform for pathological disorders such as venous ulcers, ischemic wounds and keloid scarring ²⁵¹
Ophthalmology	Self-align implants	Intraocular implants have been shown to self-align by hydrostatic pressure (<i>in vivo</i> studies)	The features of self-aligning induce better outcomes in terms of intra-ocular stability of lens or intra-ocular devices ²¹²

5. CURRENT CHALLENGES AND FUTURE PERSPECTIVES

5.1. Current challenges

One of the major challenges that faces all types of implants in the body is the immune body reaction, which affects the function and durability of the implant. Although various approaches to control these reactions and engineer immune response have been explored,³²³ which remains a challenge that has to be considered when designing autonomous implants of the future. The design of such implants should consider the integration of technologies that can modulate immune response such as surface patterning, released molecules or cellular and cell component integration to these implants.³²⁴ Another important challenge to any implant, including the smart and autonomous implants would be the risk of implant-related infections.^{325, 326} Recent advances in fabricating novel materials that have antimicrobial properties and can prevent biofilm formation should be considered in the design of autonomous implant. Smart bioresponsive materials that can turn on these antimicrobial mechanisms upon exposure to microorganism by releasing drugs or changing their properties^{326, 327} should be explored and integrated. Other challenges that face implants in general include corrosion³²⁸, allergic reactions,^{329, 330} hypersensitivity reaction.³³¹ In addition to the above, there are challenges that can be more specific to autonomous implants. These include long term stability; continuous power generation and sensing capabilities and they are discussed in the following subsections. Self-aware implants have a complex system with self-powering and sensing units that require advanced engineering with multiple steps, including prototyping, testing and validation. The whole process can be time consuming and may create difficulty for the transition from lab scale to the commercial scale.

So far, studies related to autonomous implants are limited. When investigated *in vivo*, small animals have been used, making it difficult to anticipate the outcome in larger animals and in clinical studies. Existing self-powering implants have several challenging issues that need to be addressed to promote into a next generation multifunctional autonomous implant and increase their market penetration. For example, most self-powered implants depend on a single energy harvesting source, which limits their utilization for many applications. The integration of a system that depends on multiple power generation sources has also its limitations due to its limited size, efficiency, capacity and working conditions etc. The ability of energy harvesters to supply sufficient and continuous energy remains a big challenge in self-powering implants. There is no proper power management or prototype that controls the self-powering and sensing implants with time management, duration of supply and life of powering unit is not well reported. Embedding the power harvesters, electronics, sensors and other units will increase the size of the implant, which makes it difficult to implant the unit in the body. There are also the cytotoxic and genotoxic risks related to the degradation or failure of the self-powering units, or their components is another major issue to be considered for these implants. Interfunctional coordination between tissues, implants and inner parts remains a challenge that needs further research. Flexibility of the self-powering unit and its components, adhesion to the body, biosafety and degradability are other crucial parameters that need more attention in future studies.

In case of self-healing implants, the healing ability declines with time, and improvements in the mechanical properties will be required.³³² It is also a practical challenge to identify appropriate materials for producing self-healing implants that are associated with lower rates of wear and degradation. The potential side effects and long-term stability of self-healing materials are uncertain and may lead to inflammation reactions during the healing process.³³³ The issue of

biocompatibility of implants persists as a crucial concern, e.g. implants having self-healing properties by employing coatings that provide both biocompatibility and self-healing was explored.⁹⁰⁻⁹⁴ As discussed, coating metallic implants with a layer that has self-healing properties will help to repair defects autonomously and prolong the lifetime of implant.⁹⁰⁻⁹⁴ Preserving self-healing implants loaded with living cells is another challenge for large-scale clinical application.

Fabrication of autonomous implants involves a variety of technical, safety, financial and privacy difficulties that must be overcome before they can be global market. For example, fabrication of miniature sized sensors (to monitor, diagnose and detect) and nanogenerators that are integrated with the implant is a major challenge, as the transmitters, converters, detectors and other components have to be fixed in a limited area. Other crucial concern, to design specific implant geometry, dimensions and angles that need to adjust with the hard or soft bones. The time needed to construct these implants and the high cost that may occur due to the patient specific design. The coating of implants with self-healing materials will be another challenge, as these materials need to adhere with the implant and sustain for a long period of time. Reproducibility of design is another challenge, and safe procedures need to be undertaken to produce complex structures of implants. Challenges related to the manufacturing of self-healing materials include those related to included healing agents and the carrier for the healing agent, the integration with reinforcement, and the evaluation of healing efficacy.³³⁴

Challenges related to the characterization of autonomous implants include, difficulty in characterizing different functionalities in the same implant at the same time, e.g. a 3rd generation implant with self-aware, self-powering and self-actuation implant poses a special challenge for its characterization. Available standard tests may be not available. Tools needed to test these multifunctional implants may not be always efficient. There may be a need to develop new tools for defining the properties and testing of such autonomous implant efficacy. Bringing these autonomous implants to the wider implication is faced by the availability of enough and strong evidence of their superiority over conventional implants. In addition, the price of implant is likely to go higher, hence maintaining a balance would be necessary before it could be available commercially. All the components of the implants have to be sterilized, and the same sterilization protocol may not be suitable for all the components. Some materials may decompose or have phase changes during the sterilization process.

5.2. Future perspectives

Future research should focus on issues such as long-term *in vivo* studies, advanced power sources, multiple sensor system, enhancing biocompatibility of devices. The research pertaining to the *in vivo* testing should focus on the testing these implants in large animal models. In addition, scalability, cost-effectiveness, multifunctionality and commercial availability to be the focus of future studies. The risks for self-powering implants can be minimized if the implant is encapsulated using biocompatible materials, as well as by reducing the size of the inner components to form a miniaturized structure that can easily be implanted in the body. Strategies for prohibiting infections in self-healing implant, such as inhibiting biofilm formation via, surface coating,^{335, 336} functionalization of surfaces with silver nanoparticles,³³⁷ mesoporous silica³³⁸ or natural compounds,³³⁹ developing anti-adhesive medical surfaces, immobilization of antimicrobial agents or antibiotics.^{326, 327} Advanced coating techniques are required to boost implant-tissue integration. Moreover, natural polysaccharides, proteins, growth factors and biomolecules can be utilized as

coating adhesive, particularly polymers with high degree of biocompatibility and biodegradability offers substantial value. Integrating wireless technology with implant can offer additional advantages to implants where the sensors embedded in implant can monitor as well as communicate to provide real-time condition of the healing process.

Research aiming to develop tissue-mimic autonomous implants is evolving through the developments seen in individual lines required for individual autonomy characteristics, such as developing self-forming, self-regenerating, self-healing and self-powering properties. The possibility of integrating these characteristics into specific implants based on their target application and utilization is expected to be seen in future. These autonomous implants will be independent, as they will sense changes early and undertake necessary actuation required to address these changes, such as self-healing or releasing therapeutics alerting doctors and patients and may also get instructions via AI in future to take specific actions (to help or replace externally applied intervention that doctors have to carry out today). They will perform multiple functions, such as the self-aware feature can provide required mechanical support, self-power via nanogenerators and self-sensing and monitoring that provide information to doctor through data generated in the implant. Self-sensing allows us to detect any changes in implant and in the healing process of surrounding tissues or complications that may arise such as infection and will be able to alert us so intervention can be instituted before damage becomes irreversible. Moreover, real-time data from implanted sensors can provide vital information about implant integration to surrounding tissues and both healthcare personnel and the patient become informed of the status of the implant. Self-healing and regeneration can further enhance the functionality by which can create atmosphere to heal the nearby tissues and regenerate the damaged bones or tissues. Self-actuation can monitor the monitor the chemical or physical changes and trigger the release of cells, drugs, antibiotics etc.

In the early generations, autonomous implants such as self-aware, sensing implants should be able to report any aberrations form normal in their body, function or surroundings to the doctors or nurses. At later stages, when these autonomous implants become adopted in healthcare, and patients educated about them, patients may be able to follow through their electronic systems including cell phones, and report to health care to seek appropriate intervention. At these stages Changes, the implants should become more independent of external intervention and be able to recognize things go wrong and implement appropriate action, i.e. when they become really more like native tissue sin the next 40-50 years.

Autonomous implants are the beginning of a new technological revolution which will also benefit and integrate other technologies have improved the quality of implants and their diagnosis, detection of structure, reliability and safety. The integration of technologies such as computer tomography³⁴⁰ and AI³⁴¹ allows to facilitate 3D visualization of anatomical structures and improve radiographic diagnosis, precision, and efficiency of implants. For example, computed tomography has been utilized to analyze trabecular bone structure around dental implant,^{340, 342} analyzing bone remodeling around percutaneous osseo-integrated implant³⁴³ etc. Other examples include, AI-driven image analysis and deep learning algorithms enhanced the precision in dental implants, AI-driven neural implants are effective in tracking brain activity, such as the progression of Alzheimer's disease.³⁴⁴ AI algorithms for total joint arthroplasty analysis have shown promising results in the identification, implant failure and measuring implant dimensions.³⁴¹ Technological advancements enable the manipulation of implants surfaces and design, in order to reduce

peripheral damage to host tissues and provide efficient pharmaceutical remedies, e.g. in orthopedic oncology,³⁴⁵ and dental departments.³⁴⁶ The integration of nano-engineered strategies can help to design implant with structural stability, pore size appropriate for cell migration, mechanical support and drug release through the implants³⁴⁷. Self-powered sensors and advanced nanogenerators can also play a major role in designing these autonomous implants.^{17, 348, 349}

There is a significant need to develop autonomous implants with multifunctional features employing an advanced and sustained approach through the combination of all the concepts and technologies that are presented here. The key concept in designing implants lies in its safety and its effectiveness for the intended purpose. The current literature on various self-functioning implants in different sections has widened the thought process of integrating various functionalities and properties (such as minimum size and weight, low power consumption, sterilizable, low toxicity and economic aspect) in single autonomous system. Future research can pave a way for autonomous implants with self-monitoring and detecting techniques where the patient can instantly diagnose his medical condition for quick action. Extensive pre-clinical studies are required on these autonomous implants in accordance with the relevant international standards and national regulations before placing them under diverse situations. Moreover, advanced techniques such as digital planning, 3D printing and surface modification in implants will enable feasibility in implant placement and monitoring, proving better outcomes. Future implant design may focus on osteoimmunology, with emphasis from *immune evasion* to *immune reprogramming*.³²⁸

6. CONCLUSIONS

There has been important research that is carried out to develop and characterize or optimize self-healing, self-aware, self-regenerating, self-actuating, self-powering and self-oxygenated autonomous implants. Integrating these capabilities will enable the development of implants of the future that can be autonomous in the sense that they can sense surroundings, communicate, heal themselves and remodel. Autonomous implants have the potential to have multifunctional features by integration multiple components, but more research is needed to optimize implant design, material, their interactions with human body and long-term utilization. The reliability of these implants for multifunctional purposes should be evaluated before clinical practice. The studies carried out for individual self-working implants seem to have advanced incredibly, may it be self-aware, self-healing, self-powering implants, however, when combining two self-featured implants into one, the properties, stability, mechanical properties, compatibility will completely change, which needs further research. Developing an autonomous implant for a targeted application will require collaborative and interdisciplinary research considering areas like microbiology, biotechnology, chemistry, biomaterials, endoscopically assisted examinations, evaluation for treatments, and multicentered studies, so that preventive strategies can be designed. In some cases, the implants need to stay in the body for a longer duration or rest of their lives, therefore, designing the autonomous implant with multi- functionality is crucial to avoid multiple surgeries. Many aspects should be considered, for example, self-powered sensors with long term stability must be designed that can withstand multiple stretching cycles, and reliable energy harvesters, it is necessary to create advanced strategies that can generate power, as long as they are implanted inside the body. Further, proper implant shape, size and physical properties will be required to avoid damage to the surrounding tissues. We need to move forward with next generation innovations with techniques such as 3D printing, artificial intelligence, gene therapy and

nanotechnology, which will help to design much advanced autonomous implants with multifunctionalities.

Acknowledgements

This work was supported by the project MEBioSys with reg. no. CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004634, co-funded by the ERDF as part of the MŠMT and funding received by V4 Korea Project. NA acknowledges funding from the National Institutes of Health (1UG3TR003148-01), the American Heart Association (23IPA1053441), the Estonian Research Council (PRG1903), Michigan Translational Research and Commercialization Innovation Hub for AgBio (MTRAC AgBio, RG101700), Henry Ford Health, Department of Surgery (00679169) and Corewell Health Michigan State University Alliance grant.

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